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The Broken Windows Theory in Software Engineering

An experiment on technical debt propagation

Master's thesis in computer science and engineering

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CHALMERS UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY
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Abstract

Context: The term *technical debt* (TD) describes the aggregation of sub-optimal solutions that serve to impede the evolution and maintenance of a system. Some claim that the *broken windows theory* (BWT), a concept borrowed from criminology, applies to software development projects. The theory states that the presence of indications of previous crime (such as a broken window) will increase the likelihood of further criminal activity; TD could be considered the *broken windows* of software systems.

Objective: To empirically investigate the causal relationship between the TD density of a system and the propensity of developers to introduce new TD during the extension of that system. Primarily in situations where there are no significant hurdles to implementing a low TD solution (i.e., when there is no TD that practically *forces* the implementation of new TD).

Method: The study used a mixed-methods strategy consisting of a controlled experiment and accompanying follow-up interviews. The experiment had a total of 29 developers of varying experience levels complete small system extension tasks in systems with high or low TD density; most subjects completed one of each for a total of 51 solution submissions. The solutions were scanned for TD, both manually and using SonarQube. A subset of subjects volunteered to participate in interviews, the results of which were evaluated using *thematic analysis*.

Result: Bayesian data analysis revealed significant effects of TD level on the subjects' tendency to reimplement (rather than reuse) functionality, choose non-descriptive variable names, and introduce other *code smells* identified by SonarQube, all with at least 95% certainty. Additionally, subjects appeared to be, at least partially, aware of when they had introduced TD. The results of the thematic analysis were in line with the findings of the experiment.

Conclusion: Three separate significant results along with a validating qualitative result combine to form substantial evidence of the BWTs applicability to software engineering contexts.

Keywords: Software engineering, broken windows theory, technical debt, software, spread, contagious, controlled experiment, Bayesian data analysis, thematic analysis.

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1

Introduction

Contemporary software systems often have complex and constantly evolving code bases that require continuous maintenance. Martini et al. [1] found that developers waste as much as twenty-five percent of development time refactoring or otherwise accommodating previous work. The culprit is *technical debt* (TD), an accumulation of “not-quite-right” implementations that now serve to impede further development and maintenance. The costs incurred by TD often claim a sizeable portion of the budget of software development projects and are referred to as *interest* [2].

What is worse, unless actively managed, the costs of TD may increase at higher than linear rates with TD generating additional TD as well as interest [3]. Expression 1.1, inspired by Martini and Bosch [4], visualizes the recursive nature of this dynamic, which can constitute a vicious cycle if not dealt with through continuous refactoring activities.

$$\text{TD} \rightarrow \text{Interest} + (\text{TD} \rightarrow \text{Interest} + (\text{TD} \rightarrow \dots)) \quad (1.1)$$

There are multiple possible causes of this dynamic (and they are not mutually exclusive). Hunt and Thomas [5, p. 6] suggested that the most important factor is the “psychology, or culture, at work on a project.” They explained this by analogously applying the *broken windows theory* (BWT) from criminology. The BWT states that an indication of previous crimes, or even just general disorder, increases the likelihood of further crimes being committed. In their view, this holds in software development projects, where acceptance of minor defects can result in a snowball effect that causes further deterioration of not only the system, but also the culture surrounding the project.

It is a compelling argument that a developer might think that if someone else got away with being careless, perhaps they could too. From a psychological perspective, this could be explained through the lens of *norms*, where the apparent prevalence of a behavior forms a *descriptive norm*, signaling that the behavior is acceptable. It could also be that it happens through unconscious mimicry of previous work, or that it is simply a result of being less enthusiastic about the system due to the TD.

Though this *software engineering* BWT gained some traction, there appears to be no empirical evidence of its correctness. Besker et al. [6] found that the existence of TD impairs the morale of software developers, lending some credence to the theory, but did not examine the tangible effects of that decline.

This study aims to evaluate the causal relationship between the TD density of a system and the propensity of developers to introduce TD during the extension of the system. While there is some research indicating the developers often find themselves *forced* to introduce TD as a result of previous suboptimal solutions [1], our interest is in situations where no significant hurdles are preventing the developer from implementing a low TD solution. In other words, we want to know if they will adopt the negligent attitude towards the system that they may infer is acceptable, given its state.

The study utilizes a mixed-methods design where we combine the quantitative strengths of a controlled experiment with the qualitative comprehension offered by loosely structured interviews. The experiment involved software practitioners completing tasks that required the extension of small existing systems, designed specifically for the experiment, half of which we had deliberately injected with TD. Volunteering participants were subsequently interviewed, asked about their reason for choosing their particular solution, their general thoughts around TD management, and their views on the BWT in software engineering. We interpret the quantitative data from the experiment using *Bayesian data analysis* and the qualitative data produced by the interviews through *thematic analysis*.

Efficient management of TD requires an understanding of the dynamics that govern its growth and spread. The results of this study could be a first step towards formulating improved strategies to keep TD levels in check. Additionally, the experiment could be seen as a cross-disciplinary effort that could speak to the generalizability of the original BWT.

1.1 Research Questions

We have condensed the goals of this study into the following research questions. By distinguishing between *similar* and *dissimilar* TD we essentially ask whether developers mostly mimic TD they come in contact with, or if they also introduce TD of a different character than that which was previously in the system.

RQ1: How does existing technical debt affect a developer's propensity to introduce technical debt during further development of a system?

RQ1.1: How does existing technical debt affect a developer's propensity to introduce *similar* technical debt during further development of a system?

RQ1.2: How does existing technical debt affect a developer's propensity to introduce *dissimilar* technical debt during further development of a

system?

1.2 Limitations

For the practical reasons detailed in Sect. 3.1, the study is limited to the effects of two specific types of TD items (bad variable naming and code duplication) in a single programming language (**Java**).

Additionally, only effects of the *state* of the system are examined, i.e., the effects of differences in the code. Another interesting question would be how the *context* of the system influences the rate at which developers introduce TD, e.g., project guidelines and individual accountability measures. Although such effects are out of the scope of this study, they could be interesting subjects for future research.

2

Background

This section provides a synopsis of the various concepts that are discussed and utilized by this study. It will begin with a more in-depth description of the original *broken windows theory* (BWT), its origins, and how it made its way into software engineering. Next, we have included a description of the concept of *technical debt* (TD), how it differs from traditional debt, and the approaches used to identify and classify it. Finally, we provide a short introduction to *Bayesian data analysis*, the approach we used to evaluate the data, and a section on *causal inference*.

2.1 The Broken Windows Theory

If a window in a building is broken and is left unrepaired, all the rest of the windows will soon be broken.

—Wilson and Kelling, 1982 [7]

2.1.1 Building a Theory

The story of the BWT starts with an experiment conducted by Philip Zimbardo, a professor of psychology at Stanford University (who would later arrange the very famous and controversial, *Stanford prison experiment* [8]), in 1969. He placed identical cars, with no license plates and the hoods up, in Bronx, New York, and Palo Alto, California (on the Stanford campus). Zimbardo writes:

What happened in New York was unbelievable! Within ten minutes the 1959 Oldsmobile received its first auto strippers—a father, mother, and eight-year-old son. The mother appeared to be a lookout, while the son aided the father’s search of the trunk, glove compartment, and motor. /.../ In less than three days what remained was a battered, useless hulk of metal, the result of 23 incidents of destructive contact. [9, p. 287]

Meanwhile, the car left on the Stanford campus went untouched for over a week [9]. Zimbardo was not investigating the BWT, rather, he wanted to observe what kind of people committed acts of vandalism and under what circumstances [9]. However, he did (successfully) employ the BWT in trying to get some vandals to show up:

I expected that vandalism needed to be primed where it did not occur with a higher “natural” frequency. To do so, two of my graduate students (Mike Bond and Ebbe Ebbesen) and I decided to provide a better model for destruction by taking a sledgehammer to the car ourselves and then seeing if others would follow suit. /.../ that night at 12:30 a.m. three young men with pipes and bars began pounding away at the carcass so intensely that dormitory residents (a block away) shouted out for them to stop. [9, p. 290]

A sample size of one is hardly convincing. However, Zimbardo’s experiment did serve as inspiration for James Q. Wilson (a professor of political science at Harvard) and George L. Kelling (a criminologist researching at the National Police Foundation) to write *Broken Windows: The police and neighborhood safety* [7]. The text is no academic paper; rather, it is an opinion piece that was published by “The Atlantic”, a monthly magazine covering, among other things, politics, foreign affairs, and literature. The text takes the concept beyond the narrow domain of vandalism and applies to a broader context of crime and antisocial behavior. In doing so, they created what subsequently became known as the BWT.

Wilson and Kelling suggest (although they provide no evidence) that:

Window-breaking does not necessarily occur on a large scale because some areas are inhabited by determined window-breakers whereas others are populated by window-lovers; rather, one unrepaired broken window is a signal that no one cares, and so breaking more windows costs nothing. (It has always been fun.) [7]

They go on to outline a self-reinforcing process of *urban decay*. General disorder (leading to a perception of increased crime) will cause the local populace to adopt a stance of *not getting involved*, which further strengthens the impression that no one cares. Additionally, Wilson and Kelling point to the anonymity of life in a densely populated city as further exacerbating the issue and also note that relocating had become increasingly feasible for all but the poorest, creating a dynamic where those more well-off were more likely to move to a different neighborhood than address the issues plaguing their current location.

They suggest there has been a change in the role of the police, from maintaining order towards merely fighting crime, and argue that the abolishment of laws that had previously allowed the police to deal with vagrants, drunks, or merely *suspicious persons* was a mistake [7].

Arresting a single drunk or a single vagrant who has harmed no identifiable person seems unjust, and in a sense it is. But failing to do anything about a score of drunks or a hundred vagrants may destroy an entire community. A particular rule that seems to make sense in the individual case makes no sense when it is made a universal rule and applied to all cases. [7]

Wilson and Kelling acknowledge that there are risks associated with allowing law enforcement to act with such freedom but put their faith in that the selection, training, and supervision of police officers will give them a clear sense of the bounds of their authority.

2.1.2 Testing the Theory

Perhaps the most prolific example of policy shaped by the BWT is that of New York City under former mayor Rudy Giuliani and police commissioner William Bratton. The strategy adopted revolved around strictly enforcing minor crimes such as public transport fare evasion, public urination, public drinking, and graffiti. Crime rates in NYC dropped dramatically under their leadership; property crime and violent crime both dropped by over 50 percent, more than double the national average [10].

While the political leadership did not hesitate to attribute the improvement to their broken windows policing policies, the causality of this relationship has been questioned. Thacher [11] claims that other factors, such as a decline in the usage of crack cocaine, could explain the decline. Sampson and Raudenbush [12] reject any causal relationship between disorder and crime, and Harcourt [13] argues that broken windows policing is morally unjust.

Several more recent studies have provided empirical evidence supporting the BWT. Keizer et al. [14] secretly observed a number of public areas in Groningen, to some of which they had deliberately introduced disorder, e.g., graffiti, and found that it had a significant effect on further minor crime (such as graffiti or littering), but also on more serious crime such as robberies. Additionally, a 2015 meta-study found that broken window policing strategies moderately decrease crime levels [15].

The BWT has also been examined from a more psychological perspective, in the context of *normativity*. Several studies within the field have evaluated the effects of a littered environment on the propensity of subjects to litter themselves [16, 17]. Cialdini et al. [17] differentiate *descriptive* and *injunctive* norms, where the former describes what people commonly do and the latter what people *should* do. They argue that a littered environment conveys the descriptive norm that littering is acceptable [17].

2.1.3 Broken Windows in Software Engineering

The first reference to the BWT in a software engineering context appears in *The Pragmatic Programmer: From Journeyman to Master*, where authors Hunt and Thomas assert that the BWT holds in the software development context [5]. They describe the psychology and culture of a project team as the (likely) most crucial driver of *software entropy* (sometimes referred to as *software rot* and the “broken windows,” they claim, is a significant factor in shaping them [5]:

One broken window—a badly designed piece of code, a poor management decision that the team must live with for the duration of the project—is

all it takes to start the decline. If you find yourself working on a project with quite a few broken windows, it's all too easy to slip into the mindset of "All the rest of this code is crap, I'll just follow suit." [5, p. 8]

Hunt and Thomas provide no evidence to support this claim, other than referring to the 1969 Zimbardo experiment [9] and an (unsupported) assertion that anti-broken window measures have worked in New York City [5]. The only software development-specific arguments come in the form of anecdotal evidence [5]:

We've seen clean, functional systems deteriorate pretty quickly once windows start breaking. There are other factors that can contribute to software rot, and we'll touch on some of them elsewhere, but neglect accelerates the rot faster than any other factor. [5, p. 7]

The remedy, they suggest, is to fix each broken window as soon as it is discovered, keeping the code-base in pristine condition. Should that be impossible, then at the very least, it should be "boarded up" by, e.g., commenting out that section of the code or adding a "Not Implemented" message. In short, it should somehow be acknowledged that the window is broken and that it needs fixing [5].

Since its inception, the BWT in software engineering has mostly been discussed on online blogs and, sometimes using different terminology, in popular books such as *Clean Code* [18] with the occasional mention in a scientific paper [19]. Section 2.6 further explores the prevalence of the BWT in software engineering research.

2.2 Technical Debt

Shipping first time code is like going into debt. A little debt speeds development so long as it is paid back promptly with a rewrite... The danger occurs when the debt is not repaid. Every minute spent on not-quite-right code counts as interest on that debt.

—Cunningham , 1992 [20, p. 30]

When Ward Cunningham (co-author of *The Agile Manifesto* [21]) coined the metaphor in his 1992 OOPSLA experience report [20], he likely had had no idea how ubiquitous the metaphor would become. Since then, the concept of TD has gained widespread popularity and is commonly applied, not just to code but also to related concepts, resulting in terms such as *documentation technical debt* and *build technical debt* [22].

While a metaphor can convey the message in a concise and engaging manner, it does leave ample room for interpretation. In the case of TD, this opportunity has been exploited profusely. Cunningham, the originator himself, later thought that many had misunderstood his metaphor, using it as an excuse to produce low-quality code [23]. Rather than accepting a lower standard at the start of a project, he advocates doing your best given *your current understanding of the system* and accepting that this understanding will change as the project progresses [23].

Arguably, the disagreement is not as much over what would consist TD as how one should act in relation to TD. A possible explanation for this mismatch is that debt is nearly always a bad thing in the personal economy, while in finance, debt is more of a tool used to leverage equity. While Cunningham finds the debt undesirable but inevitable, some see it as a tool they can use to, e.g., get a product to the market quicker.

Technical debt is now a concept used and studied academically. While there certainly are multiple definitions to choose from, in this text, we will use the following one arrived at during the 2016 “Dagstuhl Seminar 16162: Managing Technical Debt in Software Engineering”:

In software-intensive systems, technical debt is a collection of design or implementation constructs that are expedient in the short term, but set up a technical context that can make future changes more costly or impossible. Technical debt presents an actual or contingent liability whose impact is limited to internal system qualities, primarily maintainability and evolvability. [24, p. 112]

In practice, anything from a single poorly chosen identifier to an unsuitable choice of architecture (or worse yet, the absence of one) can constitute TD. If left unmanaged, it may accumulate to the point where the project reaches what is sometimes referred to as the *technical debt singularity* [25]. At that point, working with the system is so tedious that a black hole may have as well swallowed any efforts put into it; it is simply impossible to extract any value from further extension and maintenance of the system [25]. Under these circumstances, the only way forward may be to scrap the system and start from scratch.

Barring the final solution of “jumping ship,” there is but one way to deal with accumulated TD: *refactoring*; the debt must be *repaid*. The efforts necessary to take the system from its current state to the *ideal* state (while retaining the same functionality) are what constitute the *principal* of TD.

A preferable solution may be to avoid taking on TD in the first place through various means of incentivizing the production of low TD code. However, in some contexts, TD is used in the previously mentioned financial manner; as leverage. For example, a startup may estimate that the returns generated by a shorter *time to market* will offset the costs of taking on some TD [26].

2.2.1 Limitations of the Metaphor

While using financial terminology may help bridge a communication gap between more technically proficient software engineers and more economically inclined managers or stakeholders, there are significant differences between regular debt and TD that should not be forgotten.

While, in the financial setting, the payback of a loan is (mostly) non-negotiable, and interest payments follow a simple formula (the interest rate times the principal), with TD, things are far more complex. The concepts may look similar on the surface but the underlying mechanics are different. Whereas a tiny loan follows the same logic as a large one, the smallest constituent parts of TD behave differently than their aggregate.

Consider a single suboptimal design choice in a system that would take a specific time to fix (let us say one hour) and an, in theory, infinite set of extension or refactoring tasks that this implementation would impact negatively (by varying magnitude). How large is the TD, and what is the interest rate? We may accept that the principal is one hour (though the ideal long-term solution might not be evident at present), but clearly, the interest rate must also account for the probability of each task across the infinite set [27]. Since there is only a *probability* that the interest must be paid, this individual piece of TD is perhaps better described as a technical *risk*. In a sense, TD is a collection of risks that, in aggregate, behaves like a debt. In practice, all of these risks can never be accurately accounted for; they are merely expected to average out.

2.2.2 Classification of Technical Debt

A common type of taxonomy groups TD issues according to their type; a systematic mapping study by Alves et al. identified 15 distinct types of TD [27]. This is their summary of the five types that were most frequently mentioned in their literature sample:

Design debt Refers to debt that can be discovered by analyzing the source code and identifying violations of the principles of good object-oriented design (e.g., very large or tightly coupled classes).

Architecture debt Refers to the problems encountered in product architecture, for example, violation of modularity, which can affect architectural requirements (performance, robustness, among others). Normally this type of debt cannot be paid off with simple interventions in the code, implying more extensive development activities.

Documentation debt Refers to the problems found in software project documentation and can be identified by looking for missing, inadequate, or incomplete documentation of any type.

Test debt Refers to issues found in testing activities that can affect the quality of those activities. Examples of this type of debt are planned tests that were not run, or known deficiencies in the test suite (e.g., low code coverage).

Code debt Refers to the problems found in the source code that can negatively affect the legibility of the code making it more difficult to maintain. Usually, this debt can be identified by examining the source code for issues related to bad coding practices. [27, p. 106–107]

However, they also note that certain categories, e.g., *design debt* and *code debt*, somewhat overlap; some TD items may not fit neatly into a particular category [27].

2.2.3 Identification of Technical Debt

Studying the propagation of TD requires a method for identifying it. There are multiple such methods, ranging from those that require more manual labor to those that rely on automated processes [3, 28, 6]. Some TD could be painfully apparent to developers; after all, it might be impacting their professional life on a daily basis. Simply asking project members could be a way of identifying some of the most egregious instances of TD.

Other TD can be a little more subtle. Manually scanning the code for these would generally be prohibitively time-consuming, hence a need for automation. Using *software visualization tools* can help identify certain types of TD, e.g., ball of yarn-like dependency patterns [29]. Scanning comments in order to identify *self-admitted technical debt* is an approach that has shown some promise. However, it is, for obvious reasons, limited to deliberately introduced TD. The technique appears to have seen little use outside of research [30].

Static code analysis tools see frequent use in industry and research contexts; they rely on rule sets to identify TD items, often referred to as *code smells* [27]. Some such tools even attempt to estimate the time required to fix each item [27]. This category ranges from simple linting rules that can do little beyond correcting indentation to more encompassing solutions that detect security issues and deviations from language convention.

2.3 Marrying the Metaphors

We propose to interpret TD items as the broken windows of the *software engineering-BWT* established by Hunt and Thomas [5]. In our view, several recent findings support this conceptualization.

Besker et al. [6] found TD to negatively impact developer morale, establishing a link between TD and the psychological state of those working in its presence. This lowered morale is reminiscent of the dynamic described by Wilson and Kelling in their original *Broken Windows* article, where they assert that general disorder will trigger the local inhabitants to adopt a general stance of “not getting involved” [7]. This link is further supported by a study by Olsson et al. (accepted for publication) that used the SAM (self-assessment manikin) system to map changes in affective states triggered by interaction with TD [28]. A natural continuation of that research would be to examine the effects of this psychological impact, where propagation or reproduction of TD may be one of the most exciting lines of inquiry.

2.4 Bayesian Data Analysis

Bayesian Data Analysis (BDA) differs considerably from the *frequentist* approach to data analysis [31] prevalent in most research fields (including software engineering). While either process offers the tools necessary to produce robust scientific results, the underlying philosophy is distinctly different, and the artifacts produced by BDA (e.g., graphs, estimates, and models) may feel unfamiliar to someone used to frequentist statistics. Below, we will outline some of the main points of difference.

Philosophically, in frequentist statistics, probability represents the frequency of an occurrence as produced by a physical process. In contrast, in the Bayesian paradigm, probability is more akin to a *degree of belief* in a particular model of reality [32]. Proponents of BDA argue that the latter view more closely corresponds to how we typically interpret probabilities in our day-to-day lives [31].

Bayesian data analysis allows the specification of a model, which is then fitted using empirical data through Bayesian updating [31]. This model, unlike frequentist analysis, relies on the inclusion of *prior knowledge*. If there is little prior knowledge, a weakly informative prior may be selected, while, on the other hand, if there is previous research, those findings could be used as a starting point [31].

Whereas a frequentist may end their line of inquiry by conducting a hypothesis test, the Bayesians are left with a model that they can query to their heart's content [31]. By specifying factor values to sample at, the model will predict outcomes under certain conditions [31]. The frequentist arrives at a result that is either *significant* or *insignificant*, which is entirely dependent on their (arbitrary) selection of α (which commonly is set to 0.05 in the natural sciences). Wasserstein et al. postulate that the fixation with *statistical significance* is unhealthy, and thus, they encourage a move “beyond statistical significance” [33]. Employing BDA is one way of following this suggestion which, according to Wasserstein et al., could prevent the software engineering community from ending up in a replication crisis like certain other disciplines.

2.5 Causal Inference

Causal claims are a rarity in software engineering research; for a good reason, ruling out the influence of confounding factors requires careful consideration of the research methodology applied. However, in this section, we will show that *randomized experiments*, a methodology applied by a few as little as 3% of software engineering research endeavors [34], enable inferences of causality if designed with great care [35].

Few are unfamiliar with the adage that *correlation does not equal causation* and Pearl [35] shows that causality can *never* be inferred from probabilities alone. What Pearl prescribes is an accompanying causal model in the form of a *directed acyclic graph* (DAG).

Figure 2.1: A set of DAGs portraying causal relationships. Vertices represent measures while edges represent causal relationships in the direction of the edge.

We will start by explaining the use of DAGs to model causal relationships. Figure 2.1a shows the most basic causal relationship imaginable modeled as a DAG. Here, the vertices X and Y represent two measures, and the edge implies a causal relationship between X and Y . The direction of the edge between them signifies that a change in X causes a change in Y , but *not* the other way around.

In Fig. 2.1b, a third measure has joined the causal fray. In this case, the level of Y depends on both X and Z .

In Fig. 2.1c, Y and Z depend on X , and additionally, Y depends on Z .

In Fig. 2.1d, Y still depends on X , but both X and Y depend on Z .

Given that we wish to evaluate the causal effects of X on Y and are able to measure Y , the first case, Fig. 2.1a, presents little challenge; there are *no* alternative explanations for a change in Y . Hence we can conclude that any change in Y was *caused* by a change in X .

The case in Fig. 2.1b is a little more challenging. Here, there will always be some uncertainty as to whether the change in Y was caused by the change in X or the change in Z . However, the model implies no covariation of X and Z , which means that through statistical analysis, it is possible to estimate the individual causal effects of X . There will always be a degree of uncertainty in that analysis since, after all, there is always the chance that the apparent effects were the result of random chance, but this is no different from the uncertainty of non-causal (correlational) relationships.

In Fig. 2.1c, while Y depends on Z as well as X , ultimately Z depends on X as well. This will mean that any effects of X on Y are causal, though they may not all be *direct*; instead, one must discuss *total causal effects*. In the words of Pearl “the measurement of direct effects is ascribed to an ideal laboratory”. In practice, verifying the directness of causal effects is nigh impossible since there *could* be an intermediary that has not been accounted for.

Figure 2.2: The four elementary confounds.

Finally, Fig. 2.1d shows a causal relationship where Y depends on X , but both X and Y depend on Z . In this case, any effects estimated for X on Y could actually be caused by this *confounding variable*. In this case, no causal relationship between X and Y can be inferred.

2.5.1 The Elementary Confounds

In order to establish the causality of a relationship, confounding variables *must* be avoided. We will give a brief account of the four elemental confounds [31].

The Fork

The “fork” (Fig. 2.2a) is perhaps the most treacherous of the elemental confounds, as it implies that somewhere up the chain of causality, the X and Y have a common ancestor, Z , that could be responsible for the correlation of X and Y [31]. Such an ancestor is commonly called a backdoor and must be blocked if one wishes to infer a causal relationship [31]. Finding and blocking them all can be a tricky thing, the direct causes of an effect may not be obvious, and additionally, there is never truly an *end* to the causal chain; one could be looking forever. However, there is one way around this: randomization. A random variable has, by definition, no causal ancestor [35] and, hence, can not share one with the response variable, which eliminates the risk of backdoors and, hence, the need for blocking.

The Pipe

The “pipe” occurs when there is a sequence of causal relationships, e.g., X causes Z , which causes Y , as shown in Fig. 2.2b [31]. A “pipe” does not introduce a backdoor and does not have to be blocked. However, the intermediary variable Z must not be included in the statistical model if one wishes to estimate the causal effects of X on Y since a statistical model will notice the correlation between Z and Y and distribute the effect between X and Y [31]. This does not negatively affect model performance in terms of predictive power, but when the goal is to *measure* causality, the effects should be confined to a single estimate indicating the total causal effects of X on Y , which the exclusion of Z from our model does.

The Collider

The “collider”, shown in Fig. 2.2c, occurs when a response variable Z is affected by two other variables, X and Y [31]. Even if X and Y are not associated, conditioning on their shared “child”, Z , can make it look like they are [31]. Therefore, when investigating the causal effects of X on Y , it is crucial not to include the shared “child” in the statistical model [31]. A model including such a shared “child” would allow for the effects on that child to influence the correlation of X and Y , which would then *not* be indicative of a causal relationship [31].

The Descendant

The “descendant” pattern (shown in Fig. 2.2d) is very similar to the “collider”, with the difference that the conditioning that produces the false association is not on the shared “child” but instead on the descendant of that “child” [31].

Conditioning on a descendant also partly conditions on the “child” and will produce a similar result. For the same reasons as in the case of the “collider,” the statistical model must not include a common descendent [31].

2.6 Related Literature

The purpose of this literature review is to provide a picture of the current views on the BWT in software engineering research, allowing us to position our study appropriately in relation to and potentially build upon previous research. While it is inspired by the procedures proposed by Kitchenham and Charters [36], it does not constitute a full *systematic literature review*. The significant differences between our review procedure and the guidelines proposed by Kitchenham and Charters are that we do not assess the quality of included papers and only present a limited synthesis. The review followed the procedure shown in Fig. 2.3 and the full list of search results and reasons for exclusion can be found at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4781298>.

Figure 2.3: The literature search process.

Table 2.1: Number of papers found and that passed each of the filter steps for each database. The result of the search and filtering is a total of 18 publications, one of which is a duplicate.

	Found	Filter 1	Filter 2	Filter 3
ACM DL	32	16	8	2
Elsevier (ScienceDirect)	5	3	1	1
IEEE Xplore	40	17	7	3
Springer Link	462	78	22	10
Wiley	6	4	2	2
Total	545	118	40	18

To get a broad base of publications, the search included several databases that are commonly used in software engineering:

- ACM DL
- IEEE Xplore
- Springer Link
- Elsevier (Science Direct)
- Wiley

BWT-like effects may not necessarily be discussed using the exact terminology and metaphor that we have introduced; hence a more general search query was included as a complement.

Search query 1: (software AND “broken window”) OR “software erosion” OR “software rot” OR “code rot”

Search query 2: (“technical debt” OR “code smell”) AND (grow OR spread OR contagious)

The search was restricted to the title, abstracts, and keywords, except in the case of Springer, which only supports full-text search. The search included all papers published before 2021-05-03. Additionally, we excluded books and non-English language results.

The results were filtered in multiple stages, each requiring a higher level of effort than the previous.

Filter 1: During the first pass, we only considered the title. In order to for a paper to pass, it had to somehow relate to TD propagation.

Filter 2: Next, we scrutinized the abstracts, again looking for any discussion on the propagation of TD.

Filter 3: Finally, we read the full paper and considered its relevance to our subject.

The yield of the literature search, after various filtering stages, can be seen in Table 2.1. Five additional papers were also added to the literature collection before the final steps, on the recommendations of our supervisors.

A summary focusing on findings related to the BWT is presented below. For the list to be more comprehensible, the papers were roughly categorized according to their subjects. However, categories may overlap and should not be considered a formal classification.

The first category includes papers that look into how TD and TD density evolves by analyzing software projects.

TD evolution:

“Can clean new code reduce technical debt density” [37] Investigates how TD grows as new features are added to the system. It finds that, while the total amount of TD is growing, the density decreases when new features with a lower TD density are added.

“Does migrating a monolithic system to microservices decrease the technical debt?” [38] follows the migration of a monolithic system to a micro-services system and finds that the migration reduced the rate at which TD grew in the system but that, over time, TD still grew. The study also reported that for each individual micro-service, the amount of TD was very high in the beginning but decreased as the artifact matured.

“Investigating the evolution of code smells in object-oriented systems” [39] tracks the evolution of individual instances of code smells and finds that a large portion of code smells are introduced when adding new functionality and that they are seldom removed, causing them to accumulate over time. It also finds that ‘long method smells’ grew the fastest of the code smells investigated.

“On the temporality of introducing code technical debt” [40] examines the change in *code technical debt* (CTD) over time in a set of open-source projects and attempts to correlate the amount of CTD introduced with the workload of the development teams. They found no correlation between the workload of the teams and the amount of new CTD introduced. They did, however, find that the introduction of CTD was mainly stable over time, with a few spikes.

“Studying the evolution of exception handling anti-patterns in a long-lived large-scale project” [41] Interviews practitioners and find that inexperienced developers propagate error handling anti-patterns by replicating existing practices in the codebase.

“The evolution of technical debt in the Apache ecosystem” [42] Investigates how TD evolves in projects. They find that while the absolute amount of TD increases, the TD density decreases over a project’s lifespan.

*“When and why your code starts to smell bad”*¹ [43] finds that most code smells are introduced during the creation of an artifact or feature and that when code smells are introduced during the evolution of the project, it is usually in close proximity to preexisting code-smells. They also observed that a significant portion was introduced during refactoring activities and that developers with high workloads or tight schedules were more likely to introduce them.

¹Not from search terms.

“A large-scale empirical study on self-admitted technical debt”² [44] shows that instances of self-admitted TD (SATD) increase over the lifetime of a project and that it usually takes a long time for them to be resolved. The study also finds a modest correlation between the number of SATD items and the actual internal quality.

The second category contains papers more focused on practitioners’ perception of TD. The papers often focus on the management, causes, or effects of TD.

Perception of TD:

“An empirical assessment of technical debt practices in industry” [45] Asks practitioners to identify causes of TD and what constitutes the interest of TD but do not report any findings regarding TD propagation.

“Architectural technical debt: A grounded theory” [46] Interviews practitioners and identifies perceived effects of ATD. They find that ATD is perceived to cause code smells.

“Hearing the voice of software practitioners on causes, effects, and practices to deal with documentation debt” [47] Asks practitioners to identify causes of and effects of documentation debt. Non-adaptation of good practices was the third most mentioned cause of Documentation debt. Similarly, low documentation quality (outdated/non-existent/inadequate) was a commonly mentioned effect of DD. It is worth noting that the study does not make it clear how the practitioners might have interpreted the survey and interview questions (and some answers suggest that interpretations varied). Therefore, we cannot be sure whether the mentioned effects and causes refer to the specific instance of debt or the system in general. Only the latter interpretation would support the BWT.

“Identifying and understanding architectural risks in software evolution: An empirical study” [48] identifies architectural risks during software evolution through interviews with practitioners. Propagation of preexisting TD was not reported as an identified risk.

“Monitoring and prevention: How technical debt is managed by software practitioners” [49] investigates what actions practitioners take to prevent the creation of TD and finds that adaptation of good practices is the most mentioned action.

“The practitioners’ point of view on the concept of technical debt and its causes and consequences: A design for a global family of industrial surveys and its first results from Brazil” [50] asks practitioners to identify causes of and effects of documentation debt. Non-adaptation of good practices is the fifth most mentioned cause of documentation debt. Similarly, low documentation quality (outdated/non-existent/inadequate) is a commonly mentioned effect of documentation debt. It is worth noting that the study does not make it clear how the practitioners might have interpreted the survey and interview questions (and some answers suggest that interpretations varied). Therefore, we cannot be sure if the mentioned effects and causes refer to the specific instance of

²Not from search terms.

debt or the system in general. Only the latter interpretation would support the BWT ³.

“*The sources and approaches to management of technical debt: A case study of two product lines in a middle-size Finnish software company*” [51] questions practitioners about causes of TD and identifies lack of time as the most common cause.

“*Embracing technical debt, from a startup company perspective*” ⁴ [26] studies TD management from the perspective of startups, through interaction with practitioners. It briefly mentions a possible vicious cycle involving TD and project culture but also found that some developers found TD no to be much of an issue in a static project group where everyone is aware of and used to it. They note a tendency to reduce TD before bringing new developers onto a project.

“*Software developer productivity loss due to technical debt—A replication and extension study examining developers’ development work*” ⁴ [52] finds that developers find themselves forced to introduce TD in as much as a quarter of the cases where they encounter existing TD. Suggesting TD has a *contagious* nature.

“*The voice of the developer*” ⁴ [53] proposes a vicious cycle in which messy code reduces the morale of the developers, causing them to write more messy code.

The last category holds papers that, apart from collecting data about TD or the perceptions of it, also proposes general models describing TD or its interest.

General models of TD:

“*The danger of architectural technical debt: Contagious debt and vicious circles*” [3] conceptualizes a model detailing the cause and effect of *architectural technical debt* (ATD) and finds a potentially vicious cycle through which existing ATD causes more ATD to be implemented.

“*The magnificent seven: Towards a systematic estimation of technical debt interest*” [54] evaluates a method for estimating the interest of TD. The method includes several propagation factors of ATD, but none of the factors correspond to the BWT. They find that the method corresponds very well with the estimates of both developers and product owners.

“*An empirically developed method to aid decisions on architectural technical debt refactoring: AnaConDebt*” [55] develops and evaluates a method in cooperation with industry for estimating the future cost of ATD partly based on the work by Bosch [3]. The derived method involves several propagation factors of ATD, but none of the identified factors include the BWT.

“*On the interest of architectural technical debt: Uncovering the contagious debt phenomenon*” [4] Investigates how ATD propagates and finds multiple mechanisms explaining ATD propagation. One of their identified propagation patterns is “Propagation by bad example,” indicating that developers copy the practices they see in a system.

³This paper is very similar to [47].

⁴Not from search terms.

Figure 2.4: Number of selected papers per TD type investigated, as reported by the authors. Those marked as “General” do not mention any specific type of TD, just TD *in general*.

The literature search did not result in a single paper that treats the BWT as the main subject, and it is never discussed using the *broken windows* terminology. The most common way it appears is by being brought up by interviewees as a cause or effect of TD, though whether what they refer to really is BWT effects is sometimes hard to determine without being able to ask follow-up questions. One of the most interesting entries is that by Tufano et al. [43] which found that new code smells tend to pop up in areas where code smells were already common. However, there are other possible explanations than BWT effects for that finding (e.g., it could simply be a consequence of *mature* parts of the system being edited less frequently).

The concept of TD inducing further TD is not uncommon. However, the sub-mechanisms identified are usually restricted to that building on top of TD creates further TD, or that interaction effects between TD items result in higher interest payments than would have been necessary if the items were separate. Entries most commonly discuss TD in general, although a significant portion is focused on Architectural TD, with a handful dealing with Code or Design TD. The distribution is shown in Fig. 2.4.

Thoroughly exploring a research field is facilitated by the application of a wide variety of approaches, as their characteristics vary and complement each other [56]. There are no studies using an experimental methodology; most of them are field studies or judgment studies, making causality difficult to ascertain. Figure 2.5 shows how we placed them in the ABC framework suggested by Stol et al. [56].

Perhaps this focus on more exploratory methods is a symptom of the research field being relatively new; some of the included entries explicitly state that the field has, until recently, chiefly been interested in definitions and theory-building. As shown in Fig. 2.6 most studies were published in the last few years.

Figure 2.5: Number of selected papers grouped by research strategy, using the categories proposed by Stol et al. [56]. The shaded regions indicate the count. Papers using multiple research strategies were counted in each of the utilized categories.

Figure 2.6: Number of selected papers grouped by year of publication.

2. Background

Naturally, the above sample is largely dependent on our choice of search terms. To mitigate the risk of missing valuable research, we used multiple databases and varied search terms. Our choice to include a second search term proved essential as the term *broken windows theory* appears to see little use in academia. Nevertheless, we cannot be certain that we have found all relevant papers, but the results of this literature review point towards there being limited (if any) research on the topic of the BWT in software engineering.

3

Method

Seaman [57] argues that diverse evidence gathered through multiple distinct methodologies will constitute stronger proof than evidence of a single type, a concept commonly referred to as *triangulation*. Following her advice, we opted for a mixed-methods design. The quantitative part consisted of a controlled experiment, and the qualitative component was comprised of follow-up interviews. While more effort was put towards the former, the latter could constitute an essential complement, enabling us to illustrate, clarify and contextualize the results of the quantitative analysis.

Using the software research strategy framework laid out by Stol and Fitzgerald [56], we would classify the experiment as *experimental simulation* while we would argue that the interview component belongs in the *judgment study* category. We consider them suitable complements to each other, as the former allows inference of *causality*, while the latter does not. However, a judgment study is of a more flexible and exploratory nature, allowing us to discover some finer details that the experiment might miss [56]. This chapter describes our methods for each component separately. Figure 3.1 presents a goal-question-metric breakdown of our design, as prescribed by Basili et al. [58], while Fig. 3.2 presents an overview of the steps we took in designing the experiment and the corresponding parts of this text.

3.1 The Experiment

This section describes the design and administration of the experiment and survey that constitute the quantitative component of our study. The purpose of the experiment was to isolate the effects of the independent variable, *technical debt* (TD) density, which would allow us to investigate the causal relationship.

Sections 3.1.1 through 3.1.5 detail the the development of our experimental design. Section 3.1.6 describe how we constructed the systems and tasks that our subjects would engage with. In Sect. 3.1.7 we relate the questions used to gather background information on the participants and in Sect. 3.1.8 we show our method of conducting the experiment. Section 3.1.9 is a short recount of how we validated our experimental process. In Sect. 3.1.10 we describe the process of extracting data from the experimental results and then, in Sect. 3.1.11 examine the causal relationships at play. Finally, in Sect. 3.1.12 we relay our data analysis process.

Figure 3.1: The GQM (goal, question, metric) breaks down a the overarching goal (conceptual level) into questions (operational level) that needs answering in order to satisfy the goals. Answering the question requires identification and measurement of suitable metrics (quantitative level). Qualitative data from interviews were used to further validate and provide insight into our findings.

Figure 3.2: Method overview displaying the different steps of our method and their dependencies. The boxes from left to right and their corresponding sections: Study design (Sect. 3), Experiment design (Sects. 3.1–3.1.6), Survey design (Sect. 3.1.7), Interview design (Sect. 3.2), Experiment and survey validation (Sect. 3.1.9), Participant recruitment (Sect. 3.3), Experiment and survey data collection (Sect. 3.1.8), Conducting interviews (Sect. 3.2), Data extraction and grouping (Sect. 3.1.10), Bayesian data analysis (Sect. 3.1.12), and Thematic analysis (Sect. 3.2.1).

There were a handful of practical constraints we had to account for in the design of the experiment:

Subject availability. Achieving a sufficient sample size would likely be a challenge as participating would take a fair amount of time and effort. Finding the right balance between data extracted from each subject and the attractiveness of participation was necessary. This balancing act was part of the process described in Sect. 3.1.9.

Keeping the secret. The subject needed to be unaware of the topic of our study, which would invalidate any data extracted from their participation. Sadly, being unable to tell a prospective participant about the incredibly fascinating subject of the study would hardly make them more likely to accept our invitation.

Sample size. Considering the sample size was likely going to be modest, we needed to design the experiment (and analysis method) in a way that would make the most of what we could get.

The study should preserve the anonymity of its participants. We did, however, not find this to be a significant limitation.

Participation should not require physical presence. Due to the ongoing pandemic in 2021 and the resulting government regulations and recommendations, all participant interaction had to happen remotely with help of technical aids.

With those constraints established, we arrived at the design described in the following pages.

3.1.1 Technical Debt Level: The Independent Variable

Since there is a vast, arguably infinite number of issues that constitute TD, determining a suitable subset to represent *high TD* is not a trivial task. One extreme would be to go for *a little bit of everything*, coming up with a *high number* of TD issue types and introducing them at a *low rate* (i.e., not in every place where we *could* introduce them). On the other end of the spectrum is an approach where we introduce a *single* form of TD at a *high rate*.

The former method, *high number, low rate* has some considerable drawbacks. First, what issues we could introduce were strongly dependent on the nature of the system; hence, it would be a significant challenge to design example systems where we could introduce the same extensive set of issues sporadically. Likely such systems would also be too large for a participant to comprehend in a reasonable amount of time. If there is a *broken windows theory* (BWT) effect, but only within a type of issue, then the subject must also have the opportunity to introduce that type of issue, or we could not measure the effect. Tasks that force the subject to make a large number of such decisions would be rather substantial and complex, making the (already tricky) undertaking of achieving a sufficient sample size even harder.

The latter method, *low number, high rate* is not without its issues, e.g., it is possible that TD issues could vary in the magnitude of their BWT effect and that the single one that we choose is an inadequate representative. However, if we only have to include a single one, it would be less challenging to ensure that it could be systematically introduced into various systems while also being a clear representation of TD.

The approach chosen was to go with *two* distinctly different types of issues introduced at a very high (maximal) rate. This way, we ensured that designing suitable sets of systems and tasks, henceforth referred to as *scenarios*, was feasible. It also mitigated the risk associated with choosing a single issue type as a representative for TD.

The first type of TD we chose was *bad variable names*, an issue with multiple great properties for the purposes of this study. Variables names are typically *abundant* (in the vast majority of programming languages); hence changing them for the worse would constitute a flaw that the subject would be likely to detect. Additionally, designing a task that requires the subject to introduce new variable names is not particularly difficult. Bad variable names are also a clear example of *code technical debt*. A variable whose name poorly describes its purpose will make the code less readable, which means that any time a piece of code needs to be understood, e.g., during refactoring, the process will be conceptually harder [59, 60], and hence, slower. This extra time (and associated development costs) constitute the *interest* payment that characterizes TD.

The second type we chose was *code duplication*. This issue shares the property of applying to the vast majority of programming languages; however, in other regards, it contrasts nicely with bad variable names. Notably, it may not be quite as obvious a defect, and avoiding propagation of it will usually take the developer more effort. In terms of scenario design, we found that accommodating the inclusion of code duplication and constructing tasks that a subject could solve in either manner were both feasible. Code duplication is often, but not always, an example of TD. If a duplicated (rather than reused) block of code requires changing, the developer must edit each instance, which will require additional time. However, sometimes the alternative may be inferior. Adopting a subpar architecture solely to avoid code duplication could very well result in a higher total amount of TD. Similarly, insisting on shared functionality between distant and unrelated classes may lead to excessive interdependency and complexity [61].

In many cases, however, there is a strong case that code duplication causes maintainability problems [62] and can be considered TD [27]. Classes that share a common parent (or slightly more distant ancestor) or implement the same interface are a solid example of when code reuse is feasible and desirable. Not only will it reduce the amount of work necessary during refactoring, but it will avoid unwanted divergence of the shared functionality (and any necessary divergence will be more explicit). Classifying code duplication as a particular type of TD is not straightforward. While Li et al. [63] firmly categorize it as code TD, using the taxonomy

offered by Alves et al. [27], it could be considered design TD. Further complicating matters, Besker et al. [64] argue that it is, in fact, architectural TD. For our purposes, the exact classification is not important; we are content with noting that they all agree that code duplication often constitutes TD.

3.1.2 Controlled Variables

When conducting an experiment, it is preferable to control as many factors as possible to avoid confounding. We managed to control the following variables.

Programming Language. While the TD issue types that constitute the independent variable apply to a wide variety of languages, their expression in that language could differ significantly. Because of time constraints, we could not feasibly construct scenarios in multiple languages. Additionally, comparison between different languages would be at best challenging and at worst impossible.

For several practical reasons, we chose **Java**¹ as the sole language of all scenarios. First, it is one of the most widespread programming languages in existence, not just in the industry, but it is also often the language used for teaching object-oriented programming at educational institutions (such as Chalmers University of Technology). This ensured a steady supply of students with some **Java** experience that we could use for early testing of the data collection method and a pre-study. Second, we, the authors, were both comfortable with working in **Java**.

Development Environment. There are plenty of IDEs available, each with its own helpful features that assist the user, and practically infinite customization options through plugins and linter configurations. Chances are, if the subjects used their regular IDEs, no two of them would use identical environments. Our solution was to enforce a standard, but fairly barebones, editor. The tool constructed for this purpose and the capabilities of its editor are detailed in Sect. 3.1.8.

Scenarios. While there necessarily had to be multiple scenarios, there should be no differences in the system or task between two versions of the same scenario, *except* for the inclusion of TD (i.e., the independent variable). Scenario design is thoroughly explained in Sect. 3.1.6.

System size, structure and complexity. We constructed all scenarios to be of roughly similar size, structure, and complexity. We describe this process in Sect. 3.1.6.

Tasks. We formulated the tasks to be quite similar, in every regard, in order to make our comparison meaningful. This is presented in Sect. 3.1.6.

¹<https://www.oracle.com/java/>

3.1.3 Dependent Variables

The dependent variables represent what outcomes could be affected by the variation of the independent variable. We used various measures of the amount of TD added to the system by the subject. They each either represent one type of TD item or are grouped by the identification method. We detail the data extraction process in Sect. 3.1.10.

3.1.4 Predictor Variables

What we could not control, we accounted for through the inclusion of additional predictor variables. Some otherwise possibly confounding factors could be made part of the model by gathering background information on the subjects. We outline our method of identifying and selecting these variables in Sect. 3.1.7.

3.1.5 Treatment and Scenario Allocation Scheme

In anticipation of a modest sample size, we opted for a repeated measures design, i.e., a design that would entail each subject finishing multiple tasks. The drawback of such a design is that it can produce *learning effects*, e.g., a subject may get better at a task with repetition. We took several measures to mitigate the impact of such effects:

- A subject was never given the exact same task twice. Being able to reuse a previously created solution would likely be irresistibly convenient.
- Each subject completed tasks in systems of high *and* low levels of TD; this allowed the statistical model to isolate the individual ‘baseline’ from the effect of the treatment.
- The order of the tasks was randomized.

The minimum number of tasks required to fulfill these criteria was two, each with an accompanying system that existed in a *high TD* and a *low TD* version. Hence, there would be four experimental run configurations in total, as shown in Table 3.1.

Table 3.1: Treatment Schedule.

Scenario 1 - High TD	Scenario 2 - Low TD
Scenario 1 - Low TD	Scenario 2 - High TD
Scenario 2 - High TD	Scenario 1 - Low TD
Scenario 2 - Low TD	Scenario 1 - High TD

As increasing the number of tasks to be completed by each subject beyond two would make the amount time and effort required by each participant too substantial, we adopted the design shown in Table 3.1. Scenario design is discussed in Sect. 3.1.6.

Figure 3.3: Composition of a scenario.

3.1.6 Scenario Design

What we refer to as a *scenario* is the combination of an example system and a task that requires the participant to add functionality to that system. As shown in Fig. 3.3, each scenario has two alternate versions: *low debt* as well as *high debt*, where the task description and the vast majority of the source code are identical but for the inclusion of some TD in the *high debt* version.

In designing scenarios, the following requirements were considered:

- The participants should have ample opportunity to replicate the types of TD that each respective scenario contains, yet solving the task without implementing further TD should be not just *possible* but also *feasible* (i.e., it should not take a very significant amount of extra effort).
- The systems should model some relatively familiar process; this should allow the participants to start off with some intuitive understanding of the system. There was no inherent value to this study in having the participants taking longer to understand the system they are working on.
- The systems should *somewhat* pass as “real” systems, i.e., they should give the impression that they could very well be a sub-component of an actual product. The participant, ideally, should not feel as though they are working on a “toy-system.” However, the system should also be sufficiently small that getting a basic understanding of it is not excessively time-consuming.
- The tasks should not be particularly difficult. The question is not if the participant *can* complete the task but rather in what manner they do so. A difficult task is also more likely to increase the variance in time taken to complete it, and would likely increase the drop-out rate.
- Participating in the study should not take more than an hour. Keeping the time necessary to participate relatively short was considered vital to the ability to attract participants.

- The example systems should be of high quality, containing as few defects as possible except for the ones deliberately introduced. In order to achieve this, a great deal of care and effort was put into the design of these example systems. The code was subjected to static code analysis with **SonarQube** (using rules from **Stylechecker** as well as **CodeHawk**), and finally, the code was also commented on by members of a focus group as described in Sect. 3.1.9.
- The scenarios should be similar enough that meaningful comparisons of the results were possible.

At first, we tried to find existing systems and tasks that might fit our criteria. *The Qualitas Corpus* [65] seemed an interesting source of example systems; however, we found that none were small enough for a participant to parse in a reasonable amount of time. We also consulted textbooks on good programming practices, such as *The Pragmatic Programmer* [5] and *Clean Code* [18] but the toy systems portrayed there were simply *too* small. With no other options seemingly available, we resorted to designing the tasks and systems ourselves.

Introducing Technical Debt

The experimental design specifies the inclusion of two types of TD (in the *high debt* versions of the scenarios), *bad variable names* and *code duplication*. The reasons for our selection of variables are discussed in Sect. 3.1.1.

Bad variable names were introduced as follows:

- Single word variable names were replaced with their first letter, e.g., `user` became `u`.
- Multiple word names were replaced by the first letter of each word, e.g., `ticketType` became `tt`.
- Words in plural got to keep the ‘s’ that they often end with, e.g., `bookings` became `bs`.
- If two variables in the same context (i.e., if it changed the functionality of system or caused it to not compile) an additional letter or number was added to one of the variables.

Code duplication was introduced by changing the inheritance structure of the systems. Specifically, the class at the top of the hierarchy (excluding `Object` which is inherited by all **Java** classes) was changed into an interface. All the functionality that was previously implemented by that class was then added to the classes that used to extend it. The result is large amounts of duplication between these (former) ‘sibling’ classes. Each scenario had this procedure applied to a single inheritance hierarchy, one that is intimately related to the scenario’s task. In practice, a scenario never had more than one inheritance hierarchy.

Figure 3.4: A simplified class diagram depicting the low debt version of the system used for the ‘Booking’ task.

The ‘Booking’ Scenario

The *familiar concept* selected for the first scenario was a simple booking system, a system that tracks *bookings*, i.e., periods of time during which some entity claims exclusive access to some shared resource. In this case, the shared resources are different types of rooms that could be found on a university campus, and the entities are students and faculty members at that campus, or more simply ‘users.’

Figure 3.4 shows a class diagram depicting the system which initially has two room types, represented by classes that are both sub-types of the abstract class (low TD version) or interface (high TD version) `Room`. The first (`ClassRoom`) requires any booking to start and end on a whole hour (i.e., 14:00 is accepted but 14:01 is not), while the second (`GroupRoom`) only allows for one booking per user. The system also has a `User` (since someone has to make a booking) and an `Interval` class that is useful for keeping track of and comparing periods of time. The system has a `Main` class (omitted from the class diagrams) that contains tests that not only help the participants check that their solution fulfills the task requirement but also aids them in comprehending the system [66].

The participant is asked to implement a new class (`ComputerClassRoom`) that has all the same restrictions as `ClassRoom` but only accepts bookings during its opening hours (defined through the constructor). The full task description can be found in Appendix B.

The ‘Tickets’ Scenario

The system provided in the ‘Tickets’ scenario models a ticket finder for a public transport system. Its purpose is to find all ticket options that would be valid for a particular user and trip at a specified time. Figure 3.5 is a class diagram of the system.

Figure 3.5: A simplified class diagram depicting the low debt version of the system used for the ‘Tickets’ task.

There are two existing ticket types: `TicketTypeSingle`, which models tickets valid for a single trip, and `TicketTypeSeasonal`, which models period tickets valid for an unlimited number of trips but only during a single season (i.e., spring, summer, autumn, or winter). They are both subtypes of the abstract class (low TD version) or interface (high TD version) `TicketType`. There is also a `TicketFinder` class that contains the list of available tickets and some functions that return the subset of the list that is valid for a given trip with a certain user. The `User` class holds some basic personal information, and the `Trip` class stores the starting and end zones of a journey and the starting time. There is a `Main` class (omitted from the class diagram) that contains tests that help the participant understand the system and check that their solution fulfills the task requirements [66].

The participant is asked to implement a new class (`TicketTypeSeasonalRestricted`) that functions like `TicketTypeSeasonal` but is only valid for users of a certain occupation (defined through the constructor), e.g., students or retirees. The full task description can be found in Appendix B.

3.1.7 Survey Design

Since additional predictor variables could improve the strength of our statistical models, a set of survey questions was designed around factors that we considered somewhat likely to have predictive value. In designing the survey, these requirements were central:

- Increasing the number of predictor candidates increases the risk of finding spurious correlations; hence we should only include variables for whose validity we could make a solid case.
- The survey should be short enough to complete in less than five minutes. A longer survey would not only increase the total time commitment necessary, making participation less attractive but could also decrease the response rate.
- The survey questions should preserve the anonymity of the participant.

We divided the questions into two parts based on whether they could be answered prior to task completion or not. The former were posed before the beginning of the experiment, while the rest were answered afterward. This allowed us to be sure that our independent variable would not influence the answers to the questions asked before the start of an experimental run, meaning that we could use them as predictors in a statistical model describing a causal relationship (see Sect. 3.1.11). It also allowed us to gather background data even for partial submissions (i.e., where the participant only completed one of the two tasks they were assigned).

Pre-task Questions

This first set of questions precedes the tasks. It centers around the participants' previous education and professional experience. In this section, we only present a compressed list of the questions included; however, a more detailed description of each question along with our motivations for including it can be found in Appendix C.

1. What is the highest degree or level of education you have completed?
2. In what field did you attain that level of education?
3. How many years of professional programming experience do you have?
4. How many years of professional experience do you have working with Java?
5. Within what domain did you attain the most work-experience?
6. My most recent place of employment used peer code reviews (Yes/No)
7. My most recent place of employment used pair programming (Yes/No)
8. My most recent place of employment tracked technical debt (Yes/No)
9. My most recent place of employment had established coding standards (Yes/No)

Post-task Questions

The questions discussed in this section were presented after task completion. The questions appear twice, once per task. These questions ask the participant to rate the maintainability of the system as well as the impact on that by the additions they submitted. For this, we found Likert-scales the most suitable solution, and so we will briefly motivate our design of these scales.

There is evidence that more finely graded scales may provide more accurate data (though this effect quickly diminishes after ten or so levels) [67]. However, a large number of choices cause an increase in the cognitive load of the person taking the survey [68]. Our choice fell on a seven-step scale. We labeled every response category since unlabeled scales require the survey-taker to ‘mentally label’ the alternatives themselves, a seemingly pointless exercise that might dissuade them from completing the survey [68]. Furthermore, selectively labeling (i.e., at the ends of the scale) could inflate the rate of extreme value responses [69].

For these questions, we used “quality (maintainability)” as a proxy for TD. The reasoning for this substitution is that subjects may not be familiar with the term *technical debt*, and while TD is not restricted to maintainability, poor maintainability implies TD. Additionally, the two TD types we introduced to the high debt versions of our systems could definitely also be categorized as defects in terms of maintainability [70, 60, 62]; hence, in this case, the concepts should correlate. Further description of the questions (e.g., the exact label texts used) is available in Appendix C.

1. The quality (maintainability) of the preexisting code in the [task name] task was:
2. The work I did in the [task name] task made the quality (maintainability) of the system:

3.1.8 Data Collection

Before describing our solution, we will briefly discuss the roads not taken. We considered several approaches ranging from simplistic code sharing using `git` to collaborating with an online provider of programming challenges such as *HackerEarth*². Some of the considered approaches and the reasons why they were not selected are listed below:

cloud9³ **web IDE** provides a fully-featured IDE with code execution capabilities in the web browser. However, the many features of cloud9 might contribute to a larger cognitive load for a participant who sees this particular environment for the first time, e.g., they might think that they have to version control their solution.

Hosted Jupyter notebooks⁴ provides a more lightweight IDE, but the design of these kinds of notebook formats is aimed towards code snippets and scripting rather than system execution. Furthermore, all available **Java** kernels build upon some special read-eval-print loop version of **Java** with commands and behavior partly distinct from standard **Java**, which participants are more likely to be used to.

Code sharing with git or zip files is appealing due to its simplicity and reliance on broadly adopted tools. However, relying on tools that the participant has to have installed introduces a whole new category of potential technical

²<https://hackerearth.com>

problems during the experiment. Furthermore, this option would require participants to execute our code on their personal, or work, computers, which they might be reluctant to do.

Developing our own tool allowed us to avoid the problems associated with the solutions described above. It also allowed us to have full control of the participants' experience and gave us the ability to modify the tool whenever a new need arose.

We call our tool the *RobotResearcher* (RR). It is a web-based environment that integrates the ACE text editor⁵ to provide a set of text editing shortcuts and syntax highlighting. The tool has access to a remote server that compiles and executes the users' code in a secure environment. The main benefits of RR were:

- It (to a large extent) ensured that all participants would be working in a similar digital environment. If each participant used their regular IDE and linter ruleset, that could produce large amounts of 'automatic' changes.
- It allowed participants to get started immediately, with no time spent on wrangling their IDE, or zip files, or git repositories.
- Some participants could be using a company computer and may be reluctant to execute unknown code on it. Executing the code remotely sidestepped that.
- It allowed participants to take part in the study remotely (a prerequisite considering the ongoing pandemic with its accompanying restrictions and recommendations).
- It made the process of conducting experimental runs low effort.
- It allowed participants to participate anonymously.

The tool will remain available at <https://bwtse.github.io/RobotResearcher> for evaluation purposes. If the link is no longer functional or a supplementing text is desired, this section will provide a concise description of the tool. Additional screenshots and a description of the technical details of the tool, can be found in Appendix D.

Walk-through

This section presents a walk-through of the data collection tool developed for this study. The walk-through is from a participant's point of view to demonstrate their experience of participating in the study. The same experience is also visualized in Fig. 3.6.

The starting page requires the participant to enter the code they would have received as part of their invitation message. This code is not personal and can be used multiple times. This allowed us to send different codes to various companies or through other distribution channels, meaning we could figure out from where the participant got their code, but they could still remain anonymous. If a valid code is entered, the participant is then presented with a short introductory text and a

⁵<https://web.archive.org/web/20210509090040/https://ace.c9.io/>

3. Method

Figure 3.6: Overview of a participants experience with the data collection tool, showing the steps they had to complete. The step with dashed border was optional.

confidentiality agreement. The “Start” button is disabled until the participant has agreed to the terms.

The experimental run starts with the nine question background survey. Some were multiple choice questions, while others accept any text input. The “Submit” button is disabled until all questions have been answered. A list of the survey questions is available in Sect. 3.1.7 with a more detailed description of our reasoning for their selection and design in Appendix C.

Next, the participant is presented with the first of two tasks they have been assigned. The task view is shown in Fig 3.7 and has the following components:

1. To the right is the task description. It holds a text that briefly describes the system as well as the task that the participant is expected to perform.
2. Below the text, there is a “Run output” window, which will display anything the system sent to `stdout` or `stderr` during execution.
3. The “Run code” button compiles the system and executes the main method of the Main class.
4. The “Submit” button allows the participant to submit their solution to the current task and progress to the next stage.
5. The window containing features 1–4 can be minimized by clicking the light grey border on its left side.
6. The embedded **ACE code** editor⁶ shows the contents of the currently selected file. It supports syntax highlighting and a set of text editing shortcuts⁷.
7. The file selector on the left allows the participant to change the file that the editor displays. Right-clicking on a file name pops up a small menu where the user can choose to delete a file, rename a file, or create a new file. Choosing “Rename” or “New File” will trigger a modal window that allows the user to input a name.

⁶<https://web.archive.org/web/20210509090040/https://ace.c9.io/>

⁷List of shortcuts available at: <https://web.archive.org/web/20210502051538/https://github.com/ajaxorg/ace/wiki/Default-Keyboard-Shortcuts>

The screenshot displays the RobotResearcher tool interface for a task titled "Tickets Task". The interface is organized into several key areas:

- Navigation:** At the top, there are four tabs: "Background info", "1 Tickets Task" (active), "2 Booking Task", and "3 Final (4) Questions".
- File Explorer (Left):** A list of files is shown, including `Main.java`, `Season.java`, `Ticket.java`, `TicketFinder.java`, `TicketType.java`, `TicketTypeSeasonal.java`, `TicketTypeSingle.java`, `Trip.java`, `User.java`, and `Zone.java`. A tip indicates: "Right click on files to add new, rename and delete. Refreshing the page will reset the whole task."
- Code Editor (Center):** Displays Java code for a ticket system. The code includes package declarations, imports for `java.time`, `java.util`, and `java.util.concurrent`. It defines a `Main` class with static fields for users, ticket types, and zones, and a `main` method that initializes a `TicketFinder` and runs tests.
- Task Description (Right):**
 - 1 Tickets Task:** Explains the system models a public transport ticket system and the goal is to add a `TicketTypeSeasonalRestricted` class.
 - Task checklist:** Lists requirements:
 - Added a `TicketTypeSeasonalRestricted` class that:
 - has all the restraints that `TicketTypeSeasonal` has.
 - only is valid for the set of occupations passed to the constructor.
 - can be stored in collections of `TicketType` and be used as a substitute for `TicketType`.
 - The code compiles and passes all tests in `Main.java`.
 - Use the **Run Code** button below to test your solution.
 - Tip:** The editor supports a [set of shortcuts](#).
- Run output (Right):** Shows the result of a compilation: "Exit code: null".
- Buttons (Bottom Right):** A green **RUN CODE** button (3) and a blue **SUBMIT** button (4).

Figure 3.7: The task view of the RobotResearcher tool.

After submitting solutions to two scenarios, the participant is presented with the task evaluation survey (detailed in Sect. 3.1.7 and Appendix C). These questions are answered on a Likert scale by moving a marker to the desired level.

RobotResearcher aligns the questions in the same order as the participant completed the scenarios they pertain to.

Finally, the participant is presented with a short “thank you” message and an embedded google form where they may enter an email address if they wish to receive a copy of this report and/or make themselves available for a short follow-up interview.

The sign-ups for the follow-up interviews (see Sect. 3.2) were collected with an external tool (an embedded Google form) to preserve the participant’s anonymity.

3.1.9 Study Validation

We validated the study design and data collection tool carefully before moving on to the main study. This step was essential, considering that we created the data collection tools and scenarios ourselves rather than using established and tested resources.

Figure 3.8 shows how we iteratively validated and improved both the data collection tool and scenarios until they were ready for the main study. We used both beta group evaluations and a pre-study, aiming to resolve any significant issues before starting

the latter, which would allow us to include the results of the pre-study in our final analysis. Therefore, we selected beta evaluators who would not have been able to participate in our main experiment as they had prior knowledge of our research objective (see Sect. 3.1 for more information).

The beta evaluations had a similar structure to our standard experimental runs, except that we also asked the participants to fill out a survey simultaneously. The survey contained questions regarding their experience with both the development environment, instructions, and scenarios. Some of the evaluators also provided us with additional feedback over text or audio outside of the survey. We had a total of eight beta evaluators spread out over multiple iterations. The feedback from our beta evaluations resulted in the following significant changes:

- The reflection questions were changed to be formulated similarly.
- The granularity of the Likert scales was changed.
- Some browser-specific bugs were fixed.
- Information on how to use the data collection tool was added.
- Information about key bindings (shortcuts) was added.
- A confirmation dialog when submitting a task was added.
- The forms were made navigable and submittable using only a keyboard.
- The task descriptions got multiple updates, improving readability and clarity.
- A link to useful documentation was added to a task description.
- A checklist was added to the task descriptions.
- More test cases were added to the scenarios.

Figure 3.8: Flowchart of the study validation process including beta group evaluations and a pre-study.

We only performed one pre-study, and as we did not encounter any issues that led to revisions in our scenarios or data collection tool, we used all data from the pre-study in our analysis.

3.1.10 Data Extraction

This section describes how we extracted the data used in the analysis from the code submissions and survey answers. Some data, such as survey answers, could in many

Table 3.2: Mapping between work domain answers from the survey and work domain categories used in the analysis

Category	Answers
None	0, -, 1, N/A, None, No work experience, School..., University
Adtech	Adtech
App	Android, Android Development
Automotive	Automotive, Mobility, Vehicle industry
Web	Developing full-stack websites, Web Development, Webb
Finance	Finance, Financial
Government	Government
Marketing	Marketing
Mixed	Mixed, Software development
Telecom	Telecom
Devops	Devops
E-Commerce	E-Commerce
Music	Music Industry
Embedded	Radar
Research	Research
Retail	Retail
Telecom	Telecom

Table 3.3: Mapping between education field answers from the survey and Education field categories used in the analysis

Category	Answers
Software Engineering	SE, Software Engineering, Information Technology, IT
Computer Science	Computer Science
Civil Engineering	Civil Engineering
Interaction Design	Interaction Design
Electrical Engineering	Electrical Engineering
Industrial engineering	Industrial engineering and management

cases merely be transferred into a data sheet. Other data, such as the solutions' TD levels, required the use of analysis tools or manual procedures.

In order to validate the results of any manual data extraction procedures, two researchers performed them independently and subsequently compared the results and examined and reconciled any inconsistencies.

Professional Experience

Data regarding the participants' number of years of *professional programming experience*, years of *professional Java experience*, and development practices could simply be transferred into a data sheet. The *domain* data had to be manually grouped; this grouping is presented in Table 3.2. For a list of the questions we used, see Sect. 3.1.7.

Table 3.4: Mapping between entry codes and the group value as well as a description of each code.

Entry-Codes	Group	Description
prestudy-students	Student	Student friends who participated in the prestudy.
kiwi-steel	Product Company	A Product company in the Gothenburg.
light-card	Consultant	Personal contacts at a consulting company.
cup-cd	Consultant	Personal contacts at a consulting company.
lock-cable	Friend	Friends from studying.
power-pillow	Open	Posted on Facebook.
screen-floor	Open	Posted on LinkedIn.
tv-box	Professional contact	Professional contacts from working in Gothenburg.
ring-button	Code interested	Old members of the digital systems committee of the Software engineering division at Chalmers.

Table 3.5: Task completion categories.

Score	Meaning
Not submitted	No solution was submitted.
Does not compile	The submitted solution did not compile.
Invalid solution	The submitted solution did not satisfy the requirements of the task.
Completed	The task was completed and the submission passed all checks.

Education

The level of the participants' education and the field of that education were recorded as part of the initial background survey. (see Sect. 3.1.7). Education fields were mapped as shown in Table 3.3.

Group

The participants were assigned to different groups based on the entry code they used. This grouping was useful for differentiating participants from different companies or telling students from professionals. Table 3.4 shows how the different entry-codes correspond to different groups.

Task Completion

Incomplete solutions are not necessarily comparable to complete solutions and would not be worthwhile subjects of further data extraction. However, since the level of

incompleteness could be of interest, task completion was graded on a four level scale, shown in Table 3.5, using a series of qualifiers.

The first and most rudimentary qualifier was whether the submission contained any new work of note. In order to pass, the submission must contain at least one new file containing something resembling a class or significant changes to an existing class.

The purpose of the second check was to establish whether the **Java** compiler could compile the submitted code. None of the submitted files could fail compilation with a **Java** compiler.⁸

The final check verified that the solution worked according to the task requirements. In order to accomplish this, we manually confirmed that the provided tests for the task all passed and that the solution was not hard-coded to work with those specific test cases.

Duplication

Duplication was measured by examining how much of the existing logic was *reimplemented* rather than *reused* in the submission. This manual method of measuring duplication was chosen over a static analyzing tool such as **SonarQube**. Static code analyzers generally do not report small chunks of duplication and are easily tricked by differing amounts of white space, slightly different structures, or different variable names.

The two provided scenarios have a similar structure and similar opportunities to reuse logic without major structural changes by the participant. Figure 3.9 shows the inheritance hierarchy structure discussed in this section.

Each scenario has a class/interface (A) that serves as the root class/interface for the class (C) that participants were asked to implement. There also exists a class (B) that already provides much of the logic required in class C, presenting some specific opportunities for reuse.

The opportunities for reuse are listed below:

- Class C reuses the constructor and member fields of class B
- Class C reuses the validation logic of class B (the `book` method for the booking scenario and `isValidFor` in the tickets scenario)
- If a `int hashCode()` implementation exists in class C: class C reuses the `int hashCode()` implementation of class B

Figure 3.9: Inheritance hierarchy visualization. A and B are pre-existing classes. C is the new class subjects were tasked with implementing.

⁸We used OpenJDK 16-`ea`+32

- If a `boolean equals(Object)` implementation exists in class C: class C reuses the `boolean equals(Object)` implementation of class B.

The listed opportunities for reuse only include reuse opportunities between C and B present in both the high and low debt scenario versions.

As a result, the measurement does not indicate if the duplication already present in the high debt version of the scenario has been further replicated but only concerns the functionality that is being duplicated for the first time. We chose this approach as there was no possibility of further replicating any existing duplication in the low debt scenario (there was none). A measurement including such duplication would therefore not constitute a fair comparison of the developers' choices. Scenario construction is further detailed in Sect. 3.1.6.

There are multiple ways of reusing logic. The most direct way would be to make class C inherit class B, but the participant could also make class C contain class B or break out common logic to separate methods that could be reused by class C. For the purposes of measuring duplication, we only focused on *if* the participant reused logic and did not evaluate *how* they reused logic.

Variable Names

The variable name data were divided into various metrics to avoid conflating debt introduced by code duplication with debt introduced by original development or refactoring. Since all variable names within the high debt versions are poor, copying code would introduce more poor variable names, whereas, in the low-debt version, it would not. If no distinction was made, it could heavily skew the result.

All variables were classified as either old, new, or copied. For each category, we recorded the number of good variable names and the total number of variable names, using the following classification:

- A variable was considered old if it previously existed and had not been changed in any way except name.
- A variable was considered copied if it was not an old variable and had the same type and use as a variable elsewhere in the system.
- A variable was considered new if it was not an old or copied variable.

To be considered *good*, a variable name fulfills the following requirements, inspired by (but a little more lenient than) the guidelines proposed by Butler et. al. [60]:

- It should consist of one, or multiple, full words.
- Its name should have some connection to its use and/or the concept it represents.

Table 3.6: Documentation status categories.

Score	Meaning
Correct	There was business logic documentation for the new class and it was mostly correct.
None	There was no business logic documentation for the new class.
Incor- rect	There was business logic documentation for the new class but it had major errors.

- It should follow the format of some widely used naming convention. While camel case is generally the standard for **Java**, we do not specify a standard and thus choose to generously also accept names that consistently follow other conventions such as snake case or pascal case.
- If it is used for iterating (where, e.g., `i, j` are commonly chosen names), or the variable represents something unknown (such as in the case of `equals()`) anything gets a pass.

A full list of identified variable names can be found in the data submissions repository.⁹

Documentation

We recorded whether the added business logic was documented in the source code. We considered no other documentation as business logic was the only part previously documented in the systems. Documentation could be in the form of ordinary comments or **JavaDoc**.

We assessed whether the subject had included any documentation of the added business logic and if the added documentation correctly described its behavior. The categories are described in Table 3.6.

Utility Methods

We manually recorded whether the class that the task description asks the participant to add had been equipped with `equals()` and/or `hashCode()` methods.

Lines of Code Added or Changed

The number of lines added or changed was recorded. The lines were counted using the UNIX `diff` utility.¹⁰ Empty lines and lines containing only a closing bracket were excluded from the count.

⁹Available at <https://github.com/BWTSE/Data/tree/v1.3> and <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4818445>.

¹⁰<https://web.archive.org/web/20210328223011/https://pubs.opengroup.org/onlinepubs/9699919799/utilities/diff.html>

Other Technical Debt Indicators

Beyond the already mentioned indicators of TD, we utilized the static code analyzing tool **SonarQube** to identify other issues that could be considered TD. What was recorded was the number of *issues* reported by **SonarQube** in the submitted codebase *minus* the number of issues in a version of the codebase which included a ‘perfect’ solution to the task (i.e., one where **SonarQube** could not detect any code smells). The inclusion of a ‘perfect’ solution was necessary for the reference system to compile, which is required for a complete **SonarQube** analysis. Issues in the **Main** class were excluded as it only contains tests and mock data creation.

Beyond the base set of issue identification rules (**Java Code Quality and Security**), we included three additional libraries **Checkstyle**¹¹, **Codehawk Java**¹², and **Findbugs**¹³. The result is a set of 1588 rules. Not all rules were suitable. The following criteria were grounds for rule exclusion:

- The rule duplicates another rule, which was occasionally the case, as we included multiple libraries.
- The rule represented a *possible standard*, i.e., one that may or may not be the standard at a particular institution but could not be considered part of general **Java** convention.
- The rule measures one of the things that we had already measured manually, e.g., code duplication detection rules were excluded in favor of manual inspection as we found them to be insufficiently effective.
- The rule concerns *minor* indentation and cosmetic formatting errors. Such rules would generate copious amounts of issues, drowning out all others. We also considered them invalid since most commonly used IDEs will help the user maintain proper indentation, while the provided editor would not.
- The rule did not make sense for a system as simple as the scenario codebases.
- The rule appeared not to function as intended.

Since the initial number of rules was enormous, examining each one of them was not feasible. Instead, we excluded rules in two passes where only rules that had generated an issue were examined, firstly during the development of the scenario codebases and secondly before evaluating the submissions. See Appendix E for the complete list of rules that triggered issues, whether we excluded them, and, if that was the case, a motivation.

¹¹Checkstyle available at: <https://github.com/checkstyle/sonar-checkstyle>

¹²CodeHawk available at: <https://github.com/SEPMLAB/CodeHawk>

¹³Findbugs available at: <https://github.com/spotbugs/sonar-findbugs>

Table 3.7: Scales used to rate experienced quality of system before and after completing the task.

Question	Scale
Quality of preexisting system	Very Bad - Bad - Somewhat Bad - Neutral - Somewhat Good - Good - Very Good
Quality changed by own work	Much Worse - Worse - Somewhat Worse - Neutral - Somewhat Better - Better - Much Better

Reflection Questions

The answers to the post-task reflection questions that ask the participants to rate the quality of the preexisting system and the effect of their work on the quality of the system were recorded as marked by the participant on the scales shown in Table 3.7.

Figure 3.10: DAG encoding our causal assumptions concerning the experiment. “3. Measures of introduced TD” corresponds to *logic reuse, variable, naming, Sonar-Qube issues, documentation state, and implemented utility logic*. They are actually parallel (having the exact same ingoing and outgoing edges) but were condensed into a single node to keep the graph readable. The same goes for “4. Measured personal characteristics”, which combines all the measures taken during the background survey.

3.1.11 Causal Analysis

To sum up the requirements for inferring causality; we must ensure that there are *no* “forks”, i.e., no common ancestors of our independent and dependent variables and that our statistical models do *not* contain *any* “pipes”, “colliders”, or “descendants.”

The DAG shown in Fig. 3.10 depicts the possible causal relationships between the measures we safely can include in our statistical models when we want to be able to infer causality. The causal relations of the DAG can easily be motivated. Both 1 and 2 were randomized and thus *cannot* have been affected by any other variables.

The personal characteristics (4) are measured before the participant is assigned a scenario and a TD level protecting it from any influence of 1 and 2. The task submissions, from which the measures of introduced TD were derived, did not exist before the subject started the experiment, but were products of the participants, the scenarios, and the TD levels. Hence, they could *not* have influenced the subjects' personal characteristics.

As discussed earlier (Sect. 2.5), the randomization of a variable guarantees that other variables do not influence it. Thus we can be certain that 1 (and 2) have no ancestors in common with 3, as they are both randomized, making “forks” impossible.

By visually inspecting the graph, we can ascertain that there are no “pipes” since there are no intermediate variables between our independent and dependent variables. It is also clear that there can be neither “colliders” nor “descendants” as both of those would require our dependent variable (3) to have “children”.

As can be seen in the graph, many potential variables have been deliberately left out, leaving us with a relatively simple causal model. This is due to the effect those variables would have on our ability to measure causal inference. For example, introducing “lines changed” as a predictor, which could be caused by our independent variable (1) and could affect our dependent variable (3), would introduce a “pipe”. Another example would be to introduce the participants' rating of the system, which could be influenced by both our independent variable (1) and our dependant variable (3), creating a “collider”. Including any of those two variables as predictors would make it impossible for us to infer causality.

We will end this section by pointing out that the measured personal characteristics are *not* randomized and that we can not, and will not, claim causality of any effects estimated for them. They could have numerous unmeasured ancestor variables in common with the dependent variable, creating causal backdoors that we could not have blocked.

3.1.12 Analysis Procedure

We used Bayesian data analysis (BDA) to analyze the extracted data from our experiments. We provide a short introduction that describes some of the advantages of this approach in Sect. 2.4.

A challenge with using BDA is that there is no widely accepted standard procedure. We largely followed the *Bayesian workflow* laid out by Gelman et al. [71]. However, there are many fine points to the iterative process of model building that they do not cover in detail. In such cases, consultation with the supervisors served to fill in the gaps.

We have multiple questions we would like the data to answer, each requiring its own specifically tailored model. To keep our analysis consistent, we used a uniform procedure to create and evaluate all models. Our complete analysis, conducted in ac-

cordance with the procedure detailed in this section, can be found in our replication package.¹⁴

We began the model building process by plotting the data and extracting some descriptive statistics (e.g., mean, variance, and median) to get a rough understanding of its distribution. We then created an initial model by choosing an appropriate distribution type and adding our essential predictors. We based this choice on whether the distribution type accurately described the underlying data generation process that produced the data and how well it fitted the empirical data.

After adopting a distribution and basic predictors, we also had to set priors. We did this by using the default priors (suggested by the `brm` function of the `brms` package¹⁵) as a starting point and then tuned them until we had priors that allowed for reasonable outcome values. We also made sure that our β parameters had priors that were skeptical of extreme effects. We did not encode any prior knowledge regarding the BWT into our priors since there appears to be no previous research on the subject in a software engineering context.

When we had an initial model with appropriate priors, we had to determine which predictors to include in the final model. For the models describing the amount of introduced TD, where we wanted to infer causality, we did this by creating a set of possible predictors subject to the restrictions laid out in Sect. 3.1.11. For other models, we used a more exhaustive set of predictors.

Next, we created a new model for each of our possible additional predictors and compared the extended models with each other and the initial model using leave-one-out cross-validation (specifically the version implemented by the `Stan` package `loo`¹⁶). The comparison allowed us to ascertain which predictors had significant predictive capabilities. Those predictors were then combined into a new set of expanded models. We repeated the process until there were no more predictors to combine.

To determine our final model, we started by selecting a set of interesting models from the predictor expansions based on the number of predictors they included and their relative performance in the comparison (in the replication package, we call those models *candidate models*). Then, each candidate model was subjected to further inspection, where we verified that sampling had been smooth, examined how well they estimated the independent variable, and performed an additional prior predictive check. We selected the relative top performer to be our *final model*.

As a final step, we tested some modifications to our final model that could enhance the validity of our analysis by, e.g., fitting it to all the available data and adding β parameters that provided us with extra insight. We then chose to keep those if they

¹⁴Available at <https://bwtse.github.io/Analysis>, source available at <https://github.com/BWTSE/Analysis/tree/v1.4> and <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4904595>

¹⁵We used version 2.15.1, `brms` can be found at <https://github.com/paul-buerkner/brms>

¹⁶<https://web.archive.org/web/20200814224945/https://mc-stan.org/loo/>

did not negatively impact the sampling process or significantly harmed the model's out-of-sample prediction capability.

With our final model in place, we could use it to answer our research question. This was done partially by inspecting the estimates for the β parameters we were interested in and querying the posterior probability distribution of the model, with factors fixed at various levels, and comparing the results. This final step of querying the model is crucial as it takes the general uncertainty of the model into account and provides an easy way to access effect sizes as it moves everything to the scale of the original input data [72].

3.2 The Interviews

This section describes the procedure we used to conduct the interviews that constitute the qualitative part of this study; the purpose of which was to gain further insights relating to our research questions. We also describe the process through which we analyzed the resulting material.

All participants who signed up for a follow-up interview were contacted and scheduled within a couple of days. We scheduled each to a maximum of 30 minutes, but the length could vary significantly depending on the participants' availability.

The interviews were loosely structured around a set of questions with the purpose of giving us further insight into why the participants acted as they did in the experiment. The questions were:

1. Can you describe your solutions to the tasks in the experiment?
2. Can you motivate why you choose those solutions?
3. What was your experience of the preexisting code?
4. How did the preexisting code affect you?
5. Do you have any other comments regarding the BWT in software engineering?
(This question followed a brief explanation of the topic of our study)

Interviews were documented using *field notes* as described by Seaman [57], i.e., we noted down any interesting reflections made by the interviewed participants relating to our research questions. We omitted any identifying details and, in many cases, translated the reflections from Swedish to English. Some participants who did not participate in the follow-up interviews provided us with their reflections in text. We also included such reflection in the interview material.

3.2.1 Interview Results Analysis

The resulting list of noteworthy statements was subjected to *thematic analysis* using a process largely following the steps laid out by Braun and Clarke [73], with the exception that our base material did not consist of a perfect transcription of *all*

that was said during the interviews, merely the things that we thought were of interest to the study. This is a brief description of the stages of the process [73]:

1. Familiarize yourself with the data.
2. Encode patterns in the data as *codes*.
3. Combine codes into overarching *themes*.
4. Check theme coherency and accuracy against the data, iterate themes until those criteria are fulfilled.
5. Define the themes and their contribution to the understanding of the data.

When constructing themes, we did employ a partially *deductive* approach, where we assumed some of the themes from the start (i.e., *software quality* and *system extension quality* (in terms of maintainability) since these were the areas of interest to us. The resulting set of themes was discussed and agreed upon by both of us (the authors).

3.3 Participant Recruitment

While random sampling is preferable to ensure a representative sample, it is seldom utilized in software engineering research. Amir and Ralph [74] found that less than 1 in 30 empirical studies in the field manage to secure a randomized sample. They give several explanations, like the prevalence of case studies which typically favor non-probabilistic sampling and the fact that there are no comprehensive ‘population lists’ from which to randomly sample. They note that the two most common sampling strategies are *purposive sampling* (using your best judgment to decide what constitutes a suitable sample) and *convenience sampling* (using what is readily available).

Our sample definitively was shaped by what (or rather *who*) was readily *available*, resulting in our sample being biased towards students and professionals with relatively short industry careers. However, we did put a significant amount of effort towards reaching older and more experienced developers (and there was nothing *convenient* about that process); hence, we would argue that we also exercised some judgment in the selection of the sample. In total, we were in contact with in excess of 30 companies. Additionally, we encouraged participants to invite their colleagues to participate, which would be considered *snowball sampling*.

Participants came from a wide variety of sources; some were fellow students or alumni of Chalmers University of Technology, others were recruited by previous colleagues, relatives, or friends at their respective workplaces. A handful was recruited by us reaching out to local software development companies who offered to relay our message to their employees, while a few joined as a result of a wider request for participants using social media. The sample we used for the interviews was a subset of the experiment subjects, who volunteered after completing their participation in the experiment.

4

Results

This section presents comprehensive accounts of our estimates for the wide variety of the variables we measured as well as the outcomes of our follow up interviews. We start by describing deviations from our method in the following section before presenting a description of our sample in Sect. 4.2. The results of our quantitative and qualitative methods are described separately in Sects. 4.3 and 4.4, respectively.

4.1 Method Deviations

While Sect. 3 describes the intended procedure; not everything went according to plan. This section presents any deviations made from that procedure.

The data collection tool did not report any errors but one of the participants was unable to sign up using the **Safari** web browser. We could not reproduce the problem and advised the participant to use a different browser. The subject later reported that they had successfully completed their participation, and since no errors were reported, it is unlikely to have impacted our results.

Two participants reported that they had experienced problems with the UI of the data collection tool. One of them accidentally reloaded the page and lost their progress. The other one accidentally submitted an empty solution. This lost us at least two submissions, which hurt our sample size. However, these drop-outs could be considered *random* and should not bias the sample.

One of the early participants discovered two minor mistakes in the given scenarios. We resolved¹ the mistakes upon notice and presented the revised versions to subsequent participants. Given the limited impact of the changes—they were not in a location that participants frequently modified—we find it unlikely that many participants noticed, let alone were impacted by their unfortunate presence.

¹Diff showing resolution: <https://github.com/BWTSE/Scenarios/compare/mainstudy-v1..mainstudy-v2>

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Figure 4.1: The professional programming experience distribution of participants (years). The mean is 5.20 years and the median a mere 1.5. The narrow bar on the left side of zero represents participants with *no* professional programming experience.

Figure 4.2: The distribution of professional **Java** programming experience of the participants (in years). The mean is 3.48 years and the median 0.25 years. The narrow bar on the left side of zero represents participants with *no* professional **Java** programming experience.

Figure 4.3: The distribution of the primary field within which the participants had acquired their professional experience.

4.2 Sample Description

In total, 29 subjects submitted solutions to at least one of the two tasks they were assigned. The convenience-sampling procedure employed produced a sample with some noticeable skews that reflect the nature of our personal networks and our geographical location (Gothenburg, Sweden).

A fair share of the sample was students with none or relatively little professional programming experience. Among those currently working in the industry, only a handful had more than ten years of experience. Figure 4.1 displays the full distribution of experience levels.

Since professional **Java** experience is, by definition, lower than professional general programming experience, that graph (Fig. 4.2) shows a similar pattern yet shifted slightly towards zero. Only about half of the sample had experience using **Java** in a professional setting, but they all considered themselves comfortable working with it (this was a criterion for participation).

Subjects reported working in various sections of the software industry, with “Automotive” being a little bit of a standout (likely due to Volvo Cars being a large local employer) as shown in Fig. 4.3.

As shown in Fig. 4.4, the most common educational field reported was “Software Engineering,” with “Computer Science” trailing at approximately half the incidence rate.

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A majority of participants reported having completed “some master-level studies,” with about a quarter claiming a finished master’s degree. The full distribution is shown in Fig. 4.5.

Figure 4.4: The distribution of the educational fields within which the participants acquired their education.

Figure 4.5: The distribution of the highest level of education attained by participants.

4.3 The Experiment

This section presents the estimates and some carefully selected posterior samples produced by the final models for each outcome. Including all the intermediary models described in Sect. 3.1.12 would not be feasible. Instead, we have provided a replication package that allows thorough examination and reproduction of our model development: <https://bwtse.github.io/Analysis>²

Interpreting the results

The *predictors* discussed in this section are factors that showed some predictive power on an outcome. The magnitude of the influence of a predictor on the outcome is described by a β (*parameter*) *estimate*. In Bayesian data analysis, the β estimate is not a single value but a probability density.

When interpreting the results, the mass of the β distributions in relation to zero is important as it represents the likelihood of a parameter having an effect. However, to infer anything about the *size* of that effect, the *outcome distribution* is vital as it shows the effects on the same *scale* as the data. This allows us to evaluate the *practical* effects.

All our models include β parameters for `high_debt_version` and `programming_experience` as well as a varying intercept for each participant (`session`). The β parameter for `high_debt_version` is compulsory as examining the effects produced by the existence of TD is the point of our study.

As our sample is skewed towards more junior developers, and we want some insight into how that might affect our result, we included the estimate for `programming_experience`. We considered using `java_experience` instead of `programming_experience` but, since **Java** shares many high-level concepts with other popular programming languages and all participants considered themselves familiar with **Java**, we chose to use `programming_experience` for more accurate estimates. Other parameters were included based on whether they improved the model, as described in Sect. 3.1.12.

We did not consider any interaction effects and did not add any other grouping factors than the participant identifier since they would entail a high risk of overfitting with our relatively small sample size.

Furthermore, we fitted all final models to the full data set, including participants who only completed one of the assigned tasks. Excluding the participants who did not complete both tasks made sampling easier. It assured that the data set was balanced but could also introduce a bias in the analysis. Therefore, we chose to fit the final models with all available data after confirming that the models could sample well

²Source available at <https://github.com/BWTSE/Analysis/tree/v1.4> and <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4904595>

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using the complete data set. We created a specific model to investigate any effects of `high_debt_version` on the participants' propensity to drop out (submitting no solution) or submit an invalid solution (see Sect. 4.3.6).

Table 4.1: Population level effects for the model describing logic reuse. Rows starting with (**c:**) and (**v:**) represent estimates corresponding to the constructor reuse and validation reuse outcomes respectively. The `intercept` estimates correspond to the baseline of the measurements (with all predictors set to zero, or *true* in the case of boolean values). The β estimates correspond to how much a predictor influences the outcome.

Parameter	mean	sd	l-95% CI	u-95% CI
v:intercept	-0.16	0.57	-1.30	0.96
c:intercept	-0.38	0.58	-1.53	0.74
v:β-high_debt_version:false	-1.79	0.66	-3.12	-0.54
v:β-programming_experience	0.26	0.47	-0.67	1.21
c:β-high_debt_version:false	-1.63	0.65	-2.95	-0.39
c:β-programming_experience	0.31	0.48	-0.66	1.24

Figure 4.6: β estimate distributions of the model describing reuse of the constructor logic. The shaded region marks 95% of the density and the vertical line marks the median.

Figure 4.7: β estimate distributions of the model describing reuse of the validation logic. The shaded region marks 95% of the density and the vertical line marks the median.

4.3.1 Logic Reuse

Table 4.1 as well as Figs. 4.6 and 4.7 show that the `high_debt_version` predictor has a significant effect on the outcome with well over 95% of the β estimate probability mass on the negative side of zero. The β estimate distribution for the `programming_experience` predictor is centered close to zero with significant probabilistic weight on both sides, indicating no or minimal effect. This information alone indicates that a high debt density in the preexisting codebase induces developers to reuse less. In contrast, the developers’ professional programming experience scarcely affects the amount of reused code.

The outcome distribution shown in Fig. 4.8 offers additional insights into the effects of the predictors. It shows a clear difference in the outcome depending on the TD level of the system. The effect appears to persist for all levels of professional programming experience. The model estimates that developers with 10 years of professional programming experience are 102% more likely to duplicate logic in the high debt version of the system. The corresponding number for those with no professional programming experience is 113%. Given that this model was developed in accordance with the restrictions arrived at in our *causal analysis* (Sect. 3.1.11), it is possible to make causal inferences regarding the effects of TD level (but *not* experience level).

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Figure 4.8: Outcome distribution of the model describing reuse, separated by high and low debt versions for five levels of professional programming experience (years).

Figure 4.9: β estimate distributions of the model describing variable naming. The shaded region marks 95% of the density and the vertical line marks the median.

Table 4.2: Population level effects for the model describing variable naming. The `intercept` estimate corresponds to the baseline of the measurements (with all predictors set to zero, or *true* in the case of boolean values). The β estimates correspond to how much a parameter influences the outcome.

Parameter	mean	sd	l-95% CI	u-95% CI
<code>intercept</code>	1.52	0.50	0.65	2.62
β : <code>high_debt_version:false</code>	2.48	0.57	1.41	3.64
β : <code>programming_experience</code>	0.14	0.46	-0.75	1.09

Figure 4.10: Outcome distribution of the model describing variable naming, separated by high and low debt versions as well as years of professional programming experience.

4.3.2 Variable Naming

Table 4.2 and Fig. 4.9 show that the `high_debt_version` predictor has a significant effect on the outcome with well over 95% of the probability mass on the right side of zero. Conversely, the `programming_experience` predictor's β estimate is centered around zero, indicating no or minimal effect. These results imply that a high debt density in the preexisting codebase causes developers to use non-descriptive variable names and that the developers' professional programming experience has little to no effect on the descriptiveness of their variable names.

The distribution, Fig. 4.10, shows a noteworthy difference in outcome depending on the level of `high_debt_version` predictor. The professional programming experience of the individual is not estimated to affect the outcome noticeably.

Figure 4.11 shows the distribution of the estimated rate of good variable naming for a developer with 10 years of professional programming experience introducing 10 variables. According to the depicted sample, a developer is 458% more likely to use a non-descriptive variable name whenever they introduce a variable in the presence of TD. Given that this model was developed in accordance with the restrictions arrived at in our *causal analysis* (Sect. 3.1.11), it is possible to make causal inferences regarding the effects of TD level (but *not* experience level).

Figure 4.11: Outcome distribution of the model describing variable naming. The histogram shows the estimated probability of each outcome (i.e., number of descriptive variable names) when a developer with 10 years of professional experience introduces 10 new variables

Table 4.3: Population level effects for the model describing the number of introduced SonarQube issues. The **intercept** estimate corresponds to the baseline of the measurements (with all predictors set to zero, or *true* in the case of boolean values). The β estimates correspond to how much a parameter influences the outcome.

Parameter	mean	sd	l-95% CI	u-95% CI
intercept	0.73	0.30	0.15	1.32
β :high_debt_version:false	-0.80	0.37	-1.53	-0.08
β :programming_experience	-0.23	0.23	-0.68	0.23

Figure 4.12: β estimate distributions of the model describing the number of SonarQube issues introduced. The shaded region marks 95% of the density and the vertical line marks the median.

Figure 4.13: Outcome distribution of the model describing the number of SonarQube issues, separated by high and low debt versions as well as years of professional programming experience.

Figure 4.14: Distribution of the difference in outcome of the SonarQube issues model with respect to debt level, separated by years of professional programming experience. That is, the distribution of the outcome under the assumption of high debt *minus* the outcome under the assumption of low debt. The thick vertical lines mark the medians.

4.3.3 SonarQube Issues

The β estimates presented in Table 4.3 suggest that the debt level of the system has a notable effect on the number of SonarQube issues introduced by the subject. As demonstrated by Fig. 4.12, zero is well outside the 95% credible interval of the estimated `high_debt_version` parameter distribution. The `programming_experience` β estimate is centered closer to zero, but the uneven distribution suggests that it could potentially have some effect.

The outcome distributions depicted in Fig. 4.13 show a moderate effect of the debt density of the system on the number of SonarQube issues introduced by the participant. The, somewhat unreliable, estimated effect of professional programming experience generates noticeable differences in the prediction for various experience levels, with more experience being expected to introduce fewer SonarQube issues.

Figure 4.14 shows the difference between the high and low debt version for various experience levels. The effects shown by the graph correspond to developers on average introducing 117% more issues in the high debt version for developers with 10 years of professional programming experience and 120% more issues for developers with 25 years of experience. That is, the model estimates no noticeable difference in *relative* effect. Given that this model was developed in accordance with the restrictions arrived at in our *causal analysis* (Sect. 3.1.11), it is possible to make causal inferences regarding the effects of TD level (but *not* experience level).

Table 4.4: Population level effects for the model describing utility methods implementation. Rows starting with (**h:**) and (**e:**) represent estimates corresponding to the *hashcode* method implementation and *equals* method implementation outcomes respectively. The **intercept** estimates correspond to the baseline of the measurements (with all predictors set to zero, or *true* in the case of boolean values). The β estimates correspond to how much a parameter influences the outcome.

Parameter	mean	sd	l-95% CI	u-95% CI
h:intercept	0.27	0.59	-0.86	1.45
e:intercept	0.39	0.63	-0.82	1.66
h:β-high_debt_version:false	0.13	0.65	-1.14	1.39
h:β-scenario:tickets	-1.02	0.62	-2.23	0.13
h:β-programming_experience	-0.47	0.54	-1.56	0.60
e:β-high_debt_version:false	-0.11	0.65	-1.42	1.10
e:β-scenario:tickets	-0.85	0.66	-2.16	0.43
e:β-programming_experience	-0.55	0.55	-1.64	0.51

Figure 4.15: The β estimate distributions of the model describing *equals* method implementation.

Figure 4.16: The β estimate distributions of the model describing *hashcode* method implementation.

4.3.4 Implemented Utility Methods

Table 4.4 as well as Figs. 4.15 and 4.16 show that the `high_debt_version` predictor has no or very little effect on the outcome with estimate densities almost centered around zero. Furthermore, the `programming_experience` and `scenario:tickets` predictors indicate a possible minor effect, though the 95% credible intervals of their estimates do cross zero.

The outcome distribution shown in Figs. 4.17 and 4.18 reveal no difference in terms of outcome in the high and low debt versions. However, they do show a clear difference between the scenarios and for different experience levels, indicating that developers with less experience and developers working on the booking scenario are more likely to implement utility methods.

Figure 4.17: The outcome distribution of the model describing utility method implementation separated by high and low debt versions as well as years of professional programming experience.

Figure 4.18: The outcome distribution of the model describing utility method implementation separated by high and low debt versions as well as utility method..

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Table 4.5: Population level effects for the model describing implementation of documentation. This outcome is categorical, where the categories are “correct”, “incorrect” och “none” where correct is the *base* case. Each predictor has one estimate for its effect towards the outcome being “incorrect” and one for its effect towards it being “None” (indicated by the prefixes). The `intercept` estimates correspond to the baseline of the measurements (with all predictors set to zero, or *true* in the case of boolean values). The β estimates correspond to how much that parameter influences the outcome. The model also contains estimates for work domains, that were omitted (they were not very informative and flooded the table).

Parameter	mean	sd	l-95% CI	u-95% CI
Incorr_Intercept	0.38	0.83	-1.28	1.97
None_Intercept	0.12	0.82	-1.54	1.73
Incorr_high_debt_version:false	-0.45	0.65	-1.73	0.81
Incorr_workplace_peer_review:false	-0.06	0.79	-1.58	1.49
Incorr_work_experience_programming	-0.01	0.48	-0.97	0.91
None_high_debt_version:false	0.46	0.66	-0.81	1.77
None_workplace_peer_review:false	1.04	0.80	-0.54	2.60
None_work_experience_programming	-0.44	0.51	-1.50	0.55

Figure 4.19: β estimate distributions of the model describing documentation state for outcome “Incorrect”. The shaded region marks 95% of the density and the vertical line marks the median.

Figure 4.20: The β estimate distributions of the model describing documentation state for outcome “None”. The shaded region marks 95% of the density and the vertical line marks the median.

4.3.5 Documentation State

Table 4.5 as well as Figs. 4.19 and 4.20 shows the beta coefficient estimates for the documentation state outcome, where “None” means the subject did not document the business logic of their new code, “Incorrect” that they incorrectly documented it, and “Correct” (which is the base case here) that they correctly documented their business logic. None of the estimations are particularly noteworthy; all the 95% credible intervals straddle zero.

The outcome distributions, displayed in Fig. 4.21, show no noticeable difference in outcome as a result of TD level, but there is a noticeable tendency towards the high debt systems having a higher rate of incorrect documentation. In contrast, the low debt systems more frequently have no documentation.

4.3.6 Task Completion

Table 4.6, displaying the β estimates for the task completion model, shows that debt level does not seem to have had a significant effect on a participant’s propensity to complete the task to a higher degree. Interestingly, these numbers suggest that subjects with an educational background in data science could be more likely to drop out or submit a sub-par solution than those with a software engineering background (who are estimated to have the highest rate of completion). Figure 4.22 shows the full distributions of the β estimates.

Figure 4.23 shows the estimated completion rates for tasks in high and low debt systems. To summarize, there is not much of a difference.

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Figure 4.21: The outcome distribution of the model describing documentation state for five levels of experience.

Table 4.6: Population level effects for the model describing task completion behavior. This outcome is an ordered categorical and the model is of the “sratio” family (stopping ratio) where the intercepts are derived from likelihood of stopping in a category rather than continuing into the next one. `intercept` estimates correspond to the baseline of the measurements with all predictors set to zero, or *true* in the case of boolean values. For the categorical “ef” parameters (short for *education field*) the baseline is Civil Engineering (randomly assigned). The β estimates correspond to how much that parameter appears to influence the outcome.

Parameter	mean	sd	l-95% CI	u-95% CI
<code>intercept [1]</code>	-0.93	0.43	-1.78	-0.11
<code>intercept [2]</code>	-2.63	0.62	-3.95	-1.49
<code>intercept [3]</code>	-2.32	0.58	-3.53	-1.23
β : <code>high_debt_version:false</code>	0.15	0.29	-0.41	0.73
β : <code>pair_programming:false</code>	0.44	0.31	-0.16	1.07
β : <code>ef-ComputerScience</code>	-0.30	0.31	-0.90	0.32
β : <code>ef-ElectricalEngineering</code>	-0.06	0.38	-0.80	0.69
β : <code>ef-Industrialengineering</code>	-0.12	0.40	-0.90	0.66
β : <code>ef-InteractionDesign</code>	0.09	0.38	-0.66	0.83
β : <code>ef-None</code>	0.09	0.40	-0.70	0.87
β : <code>ef-SoftwareEngineering</code>	0.34	0.33	-0.30	0.98

Figure 4.22: β estimate distributions of the model describing the level of task completion. The shaded region marks 95% of the density and the vertical line marks the median.

Figure 4.23: Outcome distributions for the model describing task completion level for high and low debt.

Table 4.7: Population level effects for the model describing time to complete task. The `intercept` estimate corresponds to the baseline of the measurements (with all predictors set to zero, or *true* in the case of boolean values). The β estimates correspond to how much a parameter influences the outcome.

Parameter	mean	sd	l-95% CI	u-95% CI
<code>intercept</code>	7.52	0.14	7.25	7.81
β : <code>high_debt_version:false</code>	-0.19	0.16	-0.50	0.11
β : <code>programming_experience</code>	0.04	0.12	-0.19	0.28

4.3.7 Time to Complete Task

Table 4.7 and Fig. 4.24 show that the `high_debt_version` predictor has some effect. A majority of the probability mass is on the negative side of zero, but the 95% credible interval clearly crosses zero. The `programming_experience` β estimate distribution is quite centered around zero, indicating no or minimal effect. This result gives an indication that a high debt level in the preexisting codebase causes developers to spend more time on the task, while the developers' professional programming experience has little to no effect on the time spent on the task.

The distribution shown in Fig. 4.25 shows a slight difference in the outcomes linked to the debt level of the system. The effect seems to be similar regardless of how much professional programming experience the individual has.

It is quite hard to see how much of the probability densities overlap in Fig. 4.25, but Fig. 4.26 shows the difference between the high and low debt densities. The difference between the densities is slight, with only a slight shift towards the positive side (meaning that preexisting technical debt makes developers spend marginally more time on a task).

Figure 4.24: The β estimate distributions of the model describing time to complete task. The shaded region marks 95% of the density and the vertical line marks the median.

Figure 4.25: Outcome distribution of the time model, separated by high and low debt versions as well as years of professional programming experience. Note that the x axis is log10 scaled.

Figure 4.26: Distribution of difference in outcome between high and low debt version of the time model, separated by years of professional programming experience. The shaded region shows the 95% high density interval of the distribution. Difference as: high debt time – low debt time.

Table 4.8: Population level effects for the model describing the participants’ rating of the system quality in terms of maintainability. The `intercept` estimates correspond to the baseline of the estimates (with all predictors set to zero, or *true* in the case of boolean values). As this model is of the *cumulative* family, it has six intercepts where `intercept [1]` is the logarithmic chance of observing the first outcome rather than the remaining six. `intercept [2]` is the chance of observing one of the first two outcomes rather than the remaining five, and so on. The β estimates correspond to how much a parameter influences the outcome.

Parameter	mean	sd	l-95% CI	u-95% CI
<code>intercept [1]</code>	-2.08	0.54	-3.21	-1.07
<code>intercept [2]</code>	-0.59	0.40	-1.41	0.17
<code>intercept [3]</code>	0.30	0.40	-0.50	1.07
<code>intercept [4]</code>	0.81	0.41	0.01	1.62
<code>intercept [5]</code>	2.07	0.47	1.16	3.04
<code>intercept [6]</code>	4.21	0.74	2.92	5.77
β : <code>high_debt_version:false</code>	1.41	0.47	0.48	2.33
β : <code>programming_experience</code>	-0.52	0.27	-1.07	-0.01

Figure 4.27: β estimate distributions of the model describing the subjects' rating of the systems quality (maintainability). The shaded region marks 95% of the density and the vertical line marks the median.

Figure 4.28: Outcome distribution of the model describing system rating in terms of quality (maintainability) with programming experienced fixed to 3 years, and separated by debt level of the system. The vertical lines represent the means.

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Figure 4.29: Outcome distribution of the model describing system rating in terms of quality (maintainability) with programming experienced fixed to 25 years, and separated by debt level of the system. The vertical lines represent the means.

Figure 4.30: Distribution of the estimated differences in system rating outcome with respect to debt level. That is, the distribution of the outcome under the assumption of high debt *minus* the outcome under the assumption of low debt. The graph is separated into 5 experience levels and the vertical lines represent the medians.

4.3.8 System Quality Rating

As shown by Table 4.8 and Fig. 4.27, this model estimates considerable effects of TD level (`high_debt_version`) and professional programming experience on the way subjects rated the the system in terms of quality (maintainability). In both cases, the 95% credible intervals do not cross zero. These results show that participants tended to rate the *high TD* as worse and more experienced programmers also, on average, give all our systems a lower rating.

The outcome distributions differ noticeably between the high and low debt cases in both our low experience (Fig. 4.28) and high experience (Fig. 4.29) cases. The average difference is about one unit on the Likert scale.

Figure 4.30, showing the distribution of outcome differences, allows us to estimate that a developer with 10 years of experience is 197% more likely to rate the high debt system as worse than the low debt system, as opposed to the other way around.

Table 4.9: Population level effects for the model describing the participants' rating of the quality of their own work in terms of maintainability. The `intercept` estimates correspond to the baseline of the estimates (with all predictors set to zero, or *true* in the case of boolean values). As this model is of the *cumulative* family, it has six intercepts where `intercept[1]` is the logarithmic chance of observing the first outcome rather than the remaining six. `intercept[2]` is the chance of observing one of the first two outcomes rather than the remaining five, and so on (understanding these details is not terribly important). The β estimates correspond to how much a parameter influences the outcome.

Parameter	mean	sd	l-95% CI	u-95% CI
<code>intercept[1]</code>	-4.81	1.25	-7.39	-2.48
<code>intercept[2]</code>	-3.53	1.07	-5.71	-1.45
<code>intercept[3]</code>	-1.46	0.98	-3.43	0.45
<code>intercept[4]</code>	1.43	0.99	-0.48	3.47
<code>intercept[5]</code>	2.17	1.02	0.20	4.24
<code>intercept[6]</code>	3.12	1.11	0.99	5.41
β : <code>var_naming_copied:good</code>	0.19	0.66	-1.10	1.52
β : <code>var_naming_new:good</code>	-0.04	0.77	-1.53	1.46
β : <code>reused_logic_validation:false</code>	-1.31	0.66	-2.62	-0.03
β : <code>equals_exists:false</code>	-0.17	0.56	-1.25	0.97
β : <code>sonarqube_issues</code>	0.09	0.31	-0.54	0.68
β : <code>documentation:incorrect</code>	-0.19	0.67	-1.51	1.12
β : <code>documentation_none</code>	-0.33	0.61	-1.53	0.91

4.3.9 Self-reported Submission Quality

Table 4.9 and Fig. 4.31 show a variety of small effects with high uncertainty. However, the effect of `reused_logic_validation:false` is significant enough that the 95% credible interval does not cross zero, indicating that the amount of duplication is strongly linked to how participant rated their own work.

Further insight is offered by Fig. 4.32, which depicts posterior distributions for two submissions, one which we would classify as bad and one we would classify as good. Although their peak is quite similar and centered around a neutral rating, the bad submission is much more likely to be given a bad rating, while the good submission is more likely to receive a high rating.

Figure 4.33 shows the distribution of differences between outcomes generated under the assumption of a *bad* submission and *good* submission. In the simulated case, the model estimates that participants are 114% more likely to rate the bad submission as worse than they were to rate the good submission as worse.

Figure 4.31: β estimate distributions of the model describing how participants rate their own work. The shaded region marks 95% of the density and the vertical line marks the median.

Figure 4.32: The outcome distribution of the model describing the participants' rating of their own work in terms of maintainability, simulated for what we consider to be a *bad* and *good* submission respectively. The vertical lines represent the means.

Figure 4.33: The distribution of differences between the participants' quality rating of their own work, simulated for what we consider to be a *bad* and *good* submission. The vertical lines represent the means. Difference as: bad submission rating – good submission rating.

4.4 The Interviews

The data set forming the basis of our thematic analysis were field notes taken during six follow-up interviews as well as additional comments received via email or other text messages from a further four participants. This section presents the results of that analysis. The interviews lasted from around fifteen minutes to, in the odd case, an hour with an estimated average of around thirty minutes (granted, we did not measure time accurately).

We arranged the themes derived through this process into the thematic map that constitutes Fig 4.34. A connection between two themes represents them appearing together in the interview material. The manner of their connection may differ between interviews.

Figure 4.34: A map of the themes produced by our thematic analysis. The oval nodes represent the themes that we had decided should be included before starting the thematic analysis. Nodes connected by vertices occurred together in the interview material.

The oval themes represent the ones that we enforced as part of our deductive approach. They are the focal points of our inquiry, the TD density or quality (maintenance) of the system, and the same properties of the new code they produce.

There is little doubt that subjects were bothered by the issues in the high TD version. Some complained that the short and non-descriptive variable names made the system difficult to understand, which affected their productivity. While expected, it is a solid indication that bad variable names are a good example of TD. We also found that some expressed a sense of discouragement or loss of enthusiasm in relation to system quality exemplified by comments such as “It was such a drag with all the bad variable names ...//...I almost didn’t finish the task”.

Refactoring was a topic frequently brought up and is very much a topic of interest in the context of TD propagation. The task descriptions explicitly stated that subjects were free to alter other parts of the system as they see fit, and most of our interviewees had taken advantage of that opportunity. Interestingly several of them connected system quality to their decision to refactor, while some argued that refactoring a system that was in such a sorry state was not worth their time, others expressed that the obvious faults were what prompted them to start refactoring. One said that the quality issues caused him to go on a “refactoring spree” another that the noticeable faults made them examine the system more closely, in search of more quality issues in need of attention.

Views on refactoring varied significantly, some older and more experienced developers favored an approach where refactoring efforts are mainly relegated to specifically dedicated time-slots: “You should devote specific sprints to refactoring and not mix it with feature development”. In their view, mixing refactoring work with new feature development results in productivity losses and results in individual developers exposing the project to the risks they associate with refactoring (instead, they favor team deliberations regarding significant refactoring decisions). Others favored a more flexible approach where they fix problems as they come across them, though admitting that “going down the rabbit hole” (having to follow a seemingly never-ending trail of interdependent issues) is a definite risk, especially when dealing with older systems whose architecture is reminiscent of a “ball of yarn”. Finally, high test quality and coverage were mentioned as a way of enabling more aggressive refactoring strategies by mitigating the associated risks.

Several participants noted that they had trouble deciding on how to name the variables in their new class when working on the high debt system. While they recognized that the current naming scheme was terrible, using a different one for their new variables would make the code less uniform, which could potentially be more confusing. One said that “it’s important to follow the style of the code already there to reduce bugs.” The optimal solution, they agreed, would be to fix all variable names (which some actually did), although one expressed regret over not having done it. This participant went on to admit that their discouragement, as a result of the quality issues, had made them focus on just getting the tests to pass as soon as possible to “be done with it”.

Our impression is that those who volunteered to be interviewed were more enthusiastic about the project, generally put more effort into their submissions than the average subject, and were excited to discuss the qualities of their particular solution.

5

Discussion

Our results concerning the introduction of further *technical debt* (TD) in the form of logic duplication, bad naming of newly created variables, and other issues discovered through the use of **SonarQube** all showed considerable effects:

- Developers are 102% more likely to duplicate existing logic in our systems with high levels of TD¹ (Sect. 4.3.1).
- Developers are 458% more likely to assign a variable a non-descriptive name in systems with high levels of TD¹ (Sect. 4.3.1).
- Developers introduce 117% more **SonarQube** issues in our systems with high levels of TD¹ (Sect. 4.3.3).

All of these were established by investigating 95% credible intervals. Taken together, it is very improbable that they are all false positives. Additionally, the results of our *causal analysis* (see Sect. 3.1.11 show that we can infer the *causality* of these relationships, i.e., pre-existing TD is the *cause* of the effects.

Finding 1 (RQ1): Existing TD increases the likelihood of developers introducing new TD when extending a system, even in cases where it is not *necessary* to do so.

Finding 2 (RQ1.1): Existing TD of a certain type increases the likelihood of developers introducing new TD of that type when extending a system, even in cases where it is not *necessary* to do so.

We found no noticeable effect of TD on a subject's propensity to include `equals()` and `hashCode()` methods for the new classes they constructed.

Similarly, we found no significant effect of pre-existing TD on the likelihood of participants *correctly* documenting their new code (Sect. 4.3.5). However, there was a tendency towards subjects introducing less *incorrect* documentation when working on low debt systems, i.e., these were more frequently left with *no* documentation, which, we would argue, is preferable. However, since the effect is relatively small and subject to a fair amount of uncertainty, we do not consider it conclusive evidence.

¹Effect estimated for a developer with 10 years of professional programming experience that is working on the tasks and systems described in Sect. 3.1.6

The limitations of our experiment design, i.e., bad variable names and code duplication coinciding, make it impossible for us to discern the effects of the former from the latter. However, the estimated impact on the introduction of general code-smells suggests that *broken windows theory* (BWT) effects are not limited to within specific types of TD items. That is, pre-existing bad variable names do not just induce the developer to implement additional poorly named variables but also other examples of TD. This finding is interesting because it suggests that developers mimicking previous work is not a sufficient explanation of BWT effects on its own.

Finding 3 (RQ1.2): Mimicry of existing instances of TD is not, alone, a sufficient explanation of BWT effects in software engineering.

During the follow-up interviews, participants did express that the flaws did make them less enthusiastic about the task at hand. One went as far as saying that they “hardly had the will to finish the task” and merely made sure the tests passed (they were then pleasantly surprised that the system they were assigned in their second task was of significantly higher quality). This is in line with previous findings of Besker et al. [6] and Olsson et al. [28]. Interestingly, and seemingly at odds with this statement, the results presented in Sect. 4.3.6 indicate that debt level does not appear to have significantly affected a subject’s propensity to drop out of the experiment.

However, given the comparatively large effects on code reuse (Finding 1) and variable naming (Finding 2), it is likely the case that mimicry is a significant driver of TD propagation in general. One participant admitted that “you think that someone else thought it should be this way, and then you follow in the same tracks” and several others raised the issue of *code uniformity*. While it may be clear that a system contains issues, if the defects are systematic, it may not necessarily be the case that breaking that uniformity is preferable. For example, using a different (but better) variable name to describe something already existing in adjacent classes could be more confusing than a bad (but consistent) naming scheme. We did anticipate this, and it is why we discerned *new* variables from *copied* variables. However, although there is no practical advantage to mimicking the bad naming scheme for *new* variables, it may be that some subjects preferred the *aesthetics* of consistently short and non-descriptive variables names.

Generally, the predictive values of the background factors gathered by our survey (Sect. 3.1.7) were small and uncertain enough that we could safely exclude them from the final models. This, of course, could be a symptom of our relatively low sample size ($N = 51$). Years of professional programming experience, which we included as a predictor in the final version of all models measuring TD outcomes, did show a small effect in the expected direction in each case (i.e., more experienced developers introduce less TD on average). However, it is critical to note that we only ever investigated background factors in relation to the amount of TD introduced, but *not* the effect of background factors on susceptibility to the BWT effects. It could be that experienced developers are less likely to be affected by existing TD,

but that would require the inclusion of *interaction effects* and our sample size could not hope to support such estimates to any degree of certainty.

Given that the code in a high TD system is both longer and harder to read, we might expect participants to spend more time in those systems. However, the results presented in Sect. 4.3.7 indicate no significant effect of TD on the amount of time the participants allocated towards completing their task. Perhaps this is an indication that developers are averse to compensating the productivity loss induced by TD with additional time, resulting in the loss of quality. This is further corroborated by some comments from our interviews, such as “I’ll just run my tests and be done with it” (when discussing their effort put into the high TD system).

Our analysis of the participants’ evaluation of their work (Sect. 4.3.9) reveals a tangible correlation between the way a subject rated their submitted changes in terms of quality (maintainability) and some of our various measures of TD. This correlation suggests that subjects were not completely oblivious regarding the TD they had introduced. Besker et al. found that developers often felt forced to introduce new TD due to existing TD, which implies an awareness of their TD creation. However, we presented participants with tasks that could feasibly be solved *without* introducing further TD, i.e., they were *not* forced to do so. Our results suggest that developers are somewhat aware of their introduction of TD even under such circumstances. From a practical perspective, this may be good news; it is likely easier to achieve change in a conscious rather than unconscious behavior.

Finding 4: Developers appear to be, at least partially, aware of their introduction of TD.

Although we argue that our results have answered the question of if there is *ever* a BWT effect, the next question may be: “is there ever *not* a BWT effect in software engineering?”. We suspect that such exceptions are possible, e.g., if a developer is not aware of the existence of a more optimal solution that would reduce their maintenance workload. In other words, could they identify a *broken window*, having never seen one that is *unbroken*? The broken window of the BWT is a message indicating general indifference; it stands to reason that for a *true* BWT effect to occur, the disorder must be apparent to the observer.

Given that we find convincing evidence of BWT effects, companies and software practitioners should continue striving towards keeping the TD density of their systems low. This is by no means a new insight; it has been advocated for by pioneers of the software industry for many years. However, our findings *validate* the claims of the advocates of the BWT and *corroborate* their anecdotal evidence. Finally, we believe our results are a small contribution towards establishing the generalizability of the BWT; we suspect it will get applied to other fields going forward.

5.1 Suggestions for Future Research

At the core of the BWT is that the *broken window* itself is not the primary cause of the undesired BWT effects; it merely communicates an atmosphere of neglect and indifference that indicates that there are no repercussions to the behavior that “broke the window”.

The *state* of the (proverbial) window is just one such indication, although perhaps the most important one. The possibility of repercussions can also be communicated by the *context* of the window. In the software engineering setting, this could be a range of factors ensuring some personal cost associated with the introduction of TD. One example would be peer code review, where a developer is always aware that some of their colleagues will read any code they submit. Not only is it likely to catch inadvertent mistakes, but the developer might do a better job in the first place, lest they be seen as less competent by their peers. The *broken windows* may still be there, but certain practices and circumstances may inoculate developers against their effects. Other examples of such factors could be continuous integration, acknowledgment of TD issues (such as a “fix me” comment), and the very nature of the programming language itself. Examining such contextual factors would be the next major step towards understanding the BWT of software engineering. This could be challenging to accomplish in a controlled experimental setting; it might require a longitudinal field experiment.

Furthermore, Wilson and Kelling [7], as well as Hunt and Thomas [5], describe a long-term cultural deterioration as a result of BWT effects. While our results support the central mechanism of the BWT, we can not confirm whether or not “broken windows” have a *lasting* impact on the culture of a project group, e.g., if a team is assigned to work with high TD systems for some time, will that affect their performance when switching back to a system of low TD density? This is a question we would like to see answered by further research.

Several of the studies that came up during our related literature review (Sect. 2.6) presented models of TD that did not even entertain the possibility of BWT effects. Rather, they exclusively discuss the dynamic of TD *forcing* new TD implementation. We deem our results convincing enough that TD researchers should consider them in future models.

Finally, we would welcome attempts to replicate the results of our experiment and variations of it using different systems and other examples of TD, perhaps with a sample size sufficient to investigate *interaction effects* and more than two levels of TD density. To facilitate any such efforts, we have made all our research materials publicly available; links are available in Appendix A.

5.2 Threats to Validity

This section discusses threats to the validity of our study. We have, as per the recommendations of Wohlin et al. [75], split this discussion into four parts:

Internal validity: Can we ensure that any measured effects are the result of the treatment and that it is not a result of some other factor which we have no control over or measurements of?

External validity: Do our findings generalize outside the scope of our experiment?

Construct validity: Do the treatments and measurements of our experiment correspond to the *constructs* of our theory?

Conclusion validity: What are the probabilities of our conclusions being correct?

5.2.1 Internal Validity

The choice of a simulated experiment allows us to achieve a high internal quality as we measure the effect of a specific treatment in an environment we control. We also took multiple additional measures to ensure that nothing other than the TD itself influenced the developers to take different actions in the two different tasks they were assigned.

We designed the experiment to ensure that it was always possible to measure the difference between a subject's performance in a high debt system and a low debt system, reducing the influence of factors that we could not control. These factors include, but are not limited to, the time of day of the experiment, which hardware they used, and their physical environment.

Another threat to internal validity is learning effects. However, randomization of the order of the scenarios and debt levels should have neutralized the impacts of any such effects on our results.

In an isolated experiment such as this, it could have been that the subjects were not particularly meticulous in their work since they did not *care* about their performance. Conversely, in practice, the opposite is more often the case. In experiment and survey research, respondents frequently elicit *social desirability bias*. That is, they may answer or perform in the manner that they think is *socially desirable* [76]. We would argue that since low TD code would be desirable, the subjects are more likely to have *overperformed* rather than the opposite.

The use of a fully automated research tool ensured that we could not influence the subject in any way while participating in the experiment. The research tool presented participants with the same interface, information, and task description no matter whether they were coding in the high debt system or the low debt system. We also denied any questions from participants during their work on the systems.

5.2.2 External Validity

Since we had to rely on volunteering subjects, i.e., something more akin to *convenience sampling* rather than random sampling, there is reason to doubt that the sample was fully representative of the population. However, the fact that background factors showed little predictive power indicates that the skew in the sample is unlikely to have affected our results.

Another concern regarding external validity is how representative our system and research environments were of real systems and natural environments; there are some disparities, e.g., the lack of symbol searching in the environment and the size of the scenarios. The contrived setting of this study could impact the generalizability of our findings. But, as noted by Stol and Fitzgerald [56], there is an inherent trade-off between the generalizability of a study conducted in a more natural environment and the precision with which measurement of behavior can be achieved in a study using a more controlled and *contrived* setting. The chosen research strategy allowed us to measure how high TD levels affect the behavior of developers, with, we would argue, high precision. This would not have been possible in a natural setting. The qualitative part of the study also helped improve the generalizability of the study as it included a question about BWT in a neutral setting, where multiple participants expressed their support of the theory.

Although the existence of BWT effects indicated by our results is generalizable, the estimated magnitudes of them are still quite specific to our system and may not apply to other contexts. The levels of our independent variable are *high* and *low*; this is not sufficient to construct a *general model* of the BWT in software engineering.

5.2.3 Construct Validity

There is a multitude of slightly differing definitions and classifications of TD; hence there may be some question as to whether our dependent variables really measure TD. Similarly, the issues that we introduced to our scenarios might not, by some standard, constitute TD. However, we would argue that they do qualify under practically every definition that we have come across while researching the subject. This is further supported by the fact that subjects noticed the defects we had introduced and agreed with our assertion that they lower maintainability, i.e., they tended to rate the *high TD* systems as worse in terms of “quality (maintainability)” (Sect. 4.3.8) and rated their own work as worse when it had more TD according to the chosen metrics (Sect. 4.3.9). In the follow-up interviews, they more frequently raised the bad variable names as an issue, but the odd participant also noted the code duplication. Taken together, we would argue that this validates our choice of TD representations.

Although we tried to keep our research question ‘secret’, some participants may have guessed that we were investigating something related to the introduction of TD. This could have caused them to act in accordance with their preconceptions of how TD is introduced. While this is not exactly hypothesis guessing, it could have

had a similar effect. One of the measures taken to avoid this was the placement of all survey questions relating to TD after both tasks to ensure that those questions could not affect the measurements.

The fact that subjects were able to drop out without completing the tasks could have masked the effects of the debt level. However, the results of our analysis of drop-out behaviors show no significant correlation between debt level and a participant's propensity to forgo their assignment.

5.2.4 Conclusion Validity

Given that a relationship was found between a preexisting high TD level and several of the outcomes measuring different kinds of TD using 95% credible intervals, there is reason to believe the validity of our conclusion is high.

We performed three out of the four types of triangulation suggested by Miller [77] to improve the conclusion validity:

Methodological triangulation The cross-validation of results obtained through the application of two distinct research methodologies, one quantitative and one qualitative, improves the validity of our conclusions.

Researcher triangulation The authors performed the manual data extraction processes on all submissions independently. Results were compared, double checked, and any inconsistencies were resolved. This practice helped us reduce any errors or biases introduced by us as researchers.

Data triangulation The usage of multiple sampling strategies, as well as the collection of data over a span of about 30 days, ensured some degree of data triangulation. The sampling strategies included snowball sampling where participants were encouraged to pass on the participation invite, convenience sampling by recruiting participants from our personal networks and purposive sampling by actively seeking out participants with more experience.

Several other studies have found, through interviews, that preexisting TD causes new TD (Sect. 2.6). While those findings do not point towards the existence of BWT effects specifically, they could be partially explained by BWT effects. Furthermore, we have found no literature contradicting the BWT in software engineering. In summary, while the literature might not corroborate our findings, it is at least aligned with them. Perhaps, the anecdotal evidence presented in popular books such as *The Pragmatic Programmer* [5] and *Clean Code* [18] could be said to lend some credence to our conclusions.

Any statistical analysis rests on a number of assumptions regarding the underlying distributions. An advantage of *Bayesian data analysis* is that the model development process makes those assumptions *explicit*. However, since there is no widely used standard governing this process, subjective assessments could have impacted the

results [71]. While we have taken great care to create models that fairly portray the data, we welcome any scrutiny of our process through the examination of our replication package.²

²Available at <https://bwtse.github.io/Analysis>, source available at <https://github.com/BWTSE/Analysis/tree/v1.4> and <https://bwtse.github.io/Analysis>.

6

Conclusion

For over twenty years, distinguished members of the software engineering community have claimed that the *broken windows theory* (BWT) is as applicable to code as its architects would argue it is to crime. This study aimed to empirically evaluate these claims that were previously supported exclusively by anecdotal evidence.

Interpreting *technical debt* (TD) as the metaphorical *broken windows*, we designed an experiment that tasked subjects with extending small **Java** systems with novel functionality. Unbeknownst to them, we had purposely riddled half of the systems with TD in the form of *bad variable names* and *code duplication*. A diverse group of 29 participants, some still students, others with more than 30 years of industry experience, submitted their solutions using a uniform development environment of our own design, the *RobotResearcher*.

From the resulting data set of 51 distinct solutions, we extracted several measures of TD, some through carefully designed manual procedures and others using the static code analyzing tool **SonarQube**. Our analysis of these metrics, utilizing Bayesian statistics, revealed considerable effects of existing TD on the subjects' propensity to reimplement, rather than reuse, functionality, choose poor names for their variables, and introduce other issues identified by **SonarQube**.

The fact that *three* distinct effects were identified (on the 95% credible interval), is substantial evidence that the dynamics of the BWT apply to the software development context. The resulting increase in issues of types other than those that we had deliberately introduced suggests that the effects are not exclusively the result of mimicry. Additionally, our finding that subjects tended to rate their work lower when it introduced more TD indicates that they were, at least partially, aware of the shortcuts they had taken.

We further examined the phenomenon through follow-up interviews with volunteering subjects which, through thematic analysis, produced results consistent with the findings of our quantitative analysis.

While our findings lend credence to the claims by programming luminaries like Hunt and Thomas, we can not confirm their assertion that the *long term effects* of the BWT dynamic is, unless actively managed, an inevitable spiral towards oblivion.

6. Conclusion

Nor can we speak to the effects on project culture or the potentially mitigative effects of certain development practices, but we hope that future studies can explore these exciting lines of inquiry.

Bibliography

- [1] A. Martini, T. Besker, and J. Bosch, “Technical debt tracking: Current state of practice,” *Science of Computer Programming*, vol. 163, pp. 42–61, 10 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scico.2018.03.007>
- [2] A. Ampatzoglou, A. Ampatzoglou, A. Chatzigeorgiou, and P. Avgeriou, “The financial aspect of managing technical debt: A systematic literature review,” *Information and Software Technology*, vol. 64, pp. 52–73, 8 2015. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.infsof.2015.04.001>
- [3] A. Martini and J. Bosch, “The danger of architectural technical debt: Contagious debt and vicious circles,” *Proceedings - 12th Working IEEE/IFIP Conference on Software Architecture, WICSA 2015*, pp. 1–10, 2015. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1109/WICSA.2015.31>
- [4] —, “On the interest of architectural technical debt: Uncovering the contagious debt phenomenon,” *Journal of Software: Evolution and Process*, vol. 29, no. 10, pp. 1–18, 2017. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1002/smr.1877>
- [5] A. Hunt and D. Thomas, *The pragmatic programmer: From journeyman to master*, 1st ed. Boston, (MA), USA: Addison-Wesley Professional, 1999.
- [6] T. Besker, H. Ghanbari, A. Martini, and J. Bosch, “The influence of technical debt on software developer morale,” *Journal of Systems and Software*, vol. 167, p. 110586, 9 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jss.2020.110586>
- [7] J. Q. Wilson and G. L. Kelling, “Broken windows: The police and neighborhood safety,” *The Atlantic Monthly*, pp. 29–38, 3 1982. [Online]. Available: https://web.archive.org/web/20210522180623if_/https://www.theatlantic.com/magazine/archive/1982/03/broken-windows/304465/
- [8] P. G. Zimbardo and G. White, “The stanford prison experiment: A simulation study of the psychology of imprisonment,” *Zimbardo Comprisonexp*, no. August, 1972. [Online]. Available: https://web.stanford.edu/dept/spec_coll/uarch/exhibits/spe/Narration.pdf
- [9] P. G. Zimbardo, “The human choice: Individuation, reason, and order versus deindividuation, impulse, and chaos,” *Nebraska symposium on motivation*, pp. 237–307, 1969. [Online]. Available: <https://stacks.stanford.edu/file/gk002bt7757/gk002bt7757.pdf>

- [10] H. Corman and N. Mocan, “Carrots, sticks and broken windows,” National Bureau of Economic Research, Cambridge, (MA), USA, Tech. Rep. 1, 7 2002. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.3386/w9061>
- [11] D. Thacher, “Order maintenance reconsidered: Moving beyond strong causal reasoning,” *The Journal of Criminal Law and Criminology*, vol. 94, no. 2, p. 381, 2004. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.2307/3491374>
- [12] R. J. Sampson and S. W. Raudenbush, “Systematic social observation of public spaces: A new look at disorder in urban neighborhoods,” *American Journal of Sociology*, vol. 105, no. 3, pp. 603–651, 1999. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1086/210356>
- [13] B. E. Harcourt, “Illusion of order: The false promise of broken windows policing,” Cambridge, (MA), USA, p. 304, 2009. [Online]. Available: http://books.google.com/books?id=mSWDy1kGUGAC&printsec=frontcover&dq=intitle:Illusion+of+Order&hl=&cd=1&source=gbs_api%5Cnpapers3://publication/uuid/C88FC395-6372-4B9E-8055-C21760415CA9
- [14] K. Keizer, S. Lindenberg, and L. Steg, “The spreading of disorder,” *Science*, vol. 322, no. 5908, pp. 1681–1685, 2008. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1161405>
- [15] A. A. Braga, B. C. Welsh, and C. Schnell, “Can policing disorder reduce crime? A systematic review and meta-analysis,” *Journal of Research in Crime and Delinquency*, vol. 52, no. 4, pp. 567–588, 7 2015. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022427815576576>
- [16] R. M. Krauss, J. L. Freedman, and M. Whitcipp, “Studies of littering,” *Journal of Experimental Social psychology*, vol. 14, pp. 109–122, 1978. [Online]. Available: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-1031\(78\)90064-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-1031(78)90064-1)
- [17] R. B. Cialdini, R. R. Reno, and C. A. Kallgren, “A focus theory of normative conduct: Recycling the concept of norms to reduce littering in public places,” *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, vol. 58, no. 6, pp. 1015–1026, 1990. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.58.6.1015>
- [18] R. C. Martin, *Clean code — A handbook of agile software craftsmanship*. Upper Saddle River, (NJ), USA: Prentice Hall, 2014, vol. 1, no. 1.
- [19] T. Sharma, G. Suryanarayana, and G. Samarthyam, “Challenges to and solutions for refactoring adoption: An industrial perspective,” *IEEE Software*, vol. 32, no. 6, pp. 44–51, 11 2015. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1109/MS.2015.105>
- [20] W. Cunningham, “The WyCash portfolio management system,” in *Addendum to the proceedings on object-oriented programming systems, languages, and applications*, vol. F1296, October 1992, pp. 29–30. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/157709.157715>
- [21] Manifesto for agile software development. Accessed: 2021-05-21. [Online]. Available: <https://web.archive.org/web/20210521013723/http://agilemanifesto.org/>

-
- [22] N. Brown, I. Ozkaya, R. Sangwan, C. Seaman, K. Sullivan, N. Zazworka, Y. Cai, Y. Guo, R. Kazman, M. Kim, P. Kruchten, E. Lim, A. MacCormack, and R. Nord, “Managing technical debt in software-reliant systems,” in *Proceedings of the FSE/SDP workshop on Future of software engineering research*. ACM Press, 2010, p. 47. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/1882362.1882373>
- [23] W. Cunningham. Debt metaphor. Accessed: 2021-0525, Transcript: <https://web.archive.org/web/20210228222853/wiki.c2.com/?WardExplainsDebtMetaphor>. [Online]. Available: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=pqeJFYwnkjE>
- [24] P. Avgeriou, P. Kruchten, I. Ozkaya, and C. Seaman, “Managing technical debt in software engineering (Dagstuhl Seminar 16162),” *Dagstuhl Reports*, vol. 6, no. 4, pp. 110–138, 2016. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.4230/DagRep.6.4.110>
- [25] A. Yates. The technical debt singularity. Accessed: 2021-05-25. [Online]. Available: <https://web.archive.org/web/20210127014037/workingwithdevs.com/technical-debt-singularity/>
- [26] T. Besker, A. Martini, R. Edirisooriya Lokuge, K. Blincoe, and J. Bosch, “Embracing technical debt, from a startup company perspective,” *Proceedings - 2018 IEEE International Conference on Software Maintenance and Evolution, ICSME 2018*, pp. 415–425, 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICSME.2018.00051>
- [27] N. S. Alves, T. S. Mendes, M. G. De Mendonça, R. O. Spinola, F. Shull, and C. Seaman, “Identification and management of technical debt: A systematic mapping study,” *Information and Software Technology*, vol. 70, pp. 100–121, 2016. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.infsof.2015.10.008>
- [28] J. Olsson, E. Risfelt, T. Besker, A. Martini, and R. Torkar, “Measuring affective states from technical debt: A psychoempirical software engineering experiment,” 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2009.10660>
- [29] T. Amanatidis, N. Mittas, A. Moschou, A. Chatzigeorgiou, A. Ampatzoglou, and L. Angelis, “Evaluating the agreement among technical debt measurement tools: building an empirical benchmark of technical debt liabilities,” *Empirical Software Engineering*, vol. 25, no. 5, pp. 4161–4204, 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10664-020-09869-w>
- [30] M. A. d. F. Farias, M. G. d. M. Neto, M. Kalinowski, and R. O. Spínola, “Identifying self-admitted technical debt through code comment analysis with a contextualized vocabulary,” *Information and Software Technology*, vol. 121, no. January 2019, 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.infsof.2020.106270>
- [31] R. McElreath, *Statistical Rethinking*. Boca Raton, (FL), USA: CRC Press, 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1201/9780429029608>
- [32] R. T. Cox, “Probability, frequency and rational expectation,” p. 280, 1946. [Online]. Available: <http://jimbeck.caltech.edu/summerlectures/references/ProbabilityFrequencyReasonableExpectation.pdf>

- [33] R. L. Wasserstein, A. L. Schirm, and N. A. Lazar, “Moving to a world beyond $p < 0.05$,” *The American Statistician*, vol. 73, no. sup1, pp. 1–19, 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1080/00031305.2019.1583913>
- [34] R. Glass, V. Ramesh, and I. Vessey, “An analysis of research in computing disciplines,” *Commun. ACM*, vol. 47, pp. 89–94, 06 2004. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/990680.990686>
- [35] J. Pearl, *Causality: Models, reasoning, and inference, second edition*, 2nd ed. New York, (NY), USA: Cambridge University Press, 2009.
- [36] K. B and C. S, “Guidelines for performing systematic literature reviews in software engineering,” 2007. [Online]. Available: <https://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/summary?doi=10.1.1.117.471>
- [37] G. Digkas, A. N. Chatzigeorgiou, A. Ampatzoglou, and P. C. Avgeriou, “Can clean new code reduce technical debt density,” *IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering*, vol. XX, no. XX, pp. 1–18, 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1109/TSE.2020.3032557>
- [38] V. Lenarduzzi, F. Lomio, N. Saarimäki, and D. Taibi, “Does migrating a monolithic system to microservices decrease the technical debt?” *Journal of Systems and Software*, vol. 169, p. 110710, 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jss.2020.110710>
- [39] A. Chatzigeorgiou and A. Manakos, “Investigating the evolution of code smells in object-oriented systems,” *Innovations in Systems and Software Engineering*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 3–18, 2014. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11334-013-0205-z>
- [40] G. Digkas, A. Ampatzoglou, A. Chatzigeorgiou, and P. Avgeriou, *On the temporality of introducing code technical debt*. Springer International Publishing, 2020, vol. 1266 CCIS. [Online]. Available: http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-58793-2_6
- [41] D. B. de Sousa, P. H. M. Maia, L. S. Rocha, and W. Viana, “Studying the evolution of exception handling anti-patterns in a long-lived large-scale project,” *Journal of the Brazilian Computer Society*, vol. 26, no. 1, pp. 1–24, 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13173-019-0095-5>
- [42] G. Digkas, M. Lungu, A. Chatzigeorgiou, and P. Avgeriou, “The evolution of technical debt in the apache ecosystem,” *Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)*, vol. 10475 LNCS, pp. 51–66, 2017. [Online]. Available: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-65831-5_4
- [43] M. Tufano, F. Palomba, G. Bavota, R. Oliveto, M. Di Penta, A. De Lucia, and D. Poshyvanyk, “When and why your code starts to smell bad,” *Proceedings - International Conference on Software Engineering*, vol. 1, pp. 403–414, 2015. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICSE.2015.59>
- [44] G. Bavota and B. Russo, “A large-scale empirical study on self-admitted technical debt,” *Proceedings - 13th Working Conference on Mining Software Repositories, MSR 2016*, pp. 315–326, 2016.

-
- [45] Z. Codabux, B. J. Williams, G. L. Bradshaw, and M. Cantor, “An empirical assessment of technical debt practices in industry,” *Journal of Software: Evolution and Process*, vol. 29, no. 10, pp. 1–32, 2017. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1002/smr.1894>
- [46] R. Verdecchia, P. Kruchten, and P. Lago, *Architectural technical debt: A grounded theory*. Springer International Publishing, 2020, vol. 12292 LNCS. [Online]. Available: http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-58923-3_14
- [47] N. Rios, L. Mendes, C. Cerdeiral, A. P. F. Magalhães, B. Perez, D. Correal, H. Astudillo, C. Seaman, C. Izurieta, G. Santos, and R. Oliveira Spínola, *Hearing the voice of software practitioners on causes, effects, and practices to deal with documentation debt*. Springer International Publishing, 2020, vol. 12045 LNCS. [Online]. Available: http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-44429-7_4
- [48] O. P. N. Slyngstad, J. Li, R. Conradi, and M. A. Babar, “Identifying and understanding architectural risks in software evolution: An empirical study,” in *Product-Focused Software Process Improvement*, A. Jedlitschka and O. Salo, Eds., vol. 5089. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2008, pp. 400–414. [Online]. Available: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-69566-0_32
- [49] B. Pérez, C. Castellanos, and D. Correal, “Monitoring and prevention: How technical debt is managed by software practitioners,” in *Trends and Applications in Information Systems and Technologies*, Á. Rocha, H. Adeli, G. Dzemyda, F. Moreira, and A. M. Ramalho Correia, Eds. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2021. [Online]. Available: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-72660-7_41
- [50] N. Rios, R. O. Spínola, M. Mendonça, and C. Seaman, “The practitioners’ point of view on the concept of technical debt and its causes and consequences: a design for a global family of industrial surveys and its first results from Brazil,” *Empirical Software Engineering*, vol. 25, no. 5, pp. 3216–3287, 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10664-020-09832-9>
- [51] J. Yli-Huumo, A. Maglyas, and K. Smolander, “The sources and approaches to management of technical debt: A case study of two product lines in a middle-size finnish software company,” *Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)*, vol. 8892, pp. 93–107, 2014. [Online]. Available: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-13835-0_7
- [52] T. Besker, A. Martini, and J. Bosch, “Software developer productivity loss due to technical debt—A replication and extension study examining developers’ development work,” *Journal of Systems and Software*, vol. 156, pp. 41–61, 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jss.2019.06.004>
- [53] I. Ozkaya, “The voice of the developer,” *IEEE Software*, vol. 36, no. 5, pp. 3–5, 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1109/MS.2019.2926545>
- [54] A. Martini and J. Bosch, “The magnificent seven: Towards a systematic estimation of technical debt interest,” *ACM International Conference*

- Proceeding Series*, vol. Part F1299, 2017. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3120459.3120467>
- [55] —, “An empirically developed method to aid decisions on architectural technical debt refactoring: AnaConDebt,” *Proceedings - International Conference on Software Engineering*, pp. 31–40, 2016. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/2889160.2889224>
- [56] K.-J. Stol and B. Fitzgerald, “The ABC of software engineering research,” *ACM Transactions on Software Engineering and Methodology*, vol. 27, no. 3, pp. 1–51, 10 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3241743>
- [57] C. Seaman, “Qualitative methods in empirical studies of software engineering,” *IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering*, vol. 25, no. 4, pp. 557–572, 1999. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1109/32.799955>
- [58] V. R. Basili and G. Caldiera, “The goal question metric paradigm,” *Encyclopedia of Software Engineering - 2 Volume Set*, vol. 2, pp. 528–532, 2000. [Online]. Available: <https://www.cs.umd.edu/~basili/publications/technical/T89.pdf>
- [59] E. Avidan and D. G. Feitelson, “Effects of variable names on comprehension: An empirical study,” *IEEE International Conference on Program Comprehension*, pp. 55–65, 2017. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICPC.2017.27>
- [60] S. Butler, M. Wermelinger, Y. Yu, and H. Sharp, “Relating identifier naming flaws and code quality: An empirical study,” *Proceedings - Working Conference on Reverse Engineering, WCRE*, pp. 31–35, 2009. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1109/WCRE.2009.50>
- [61] C. J. Kasper and M. W. Godfrey, “Cloning considered harmful: Cloning considered harmful: Patterns of cloning in software,” *Empirical Software Engineering*, vol. 13, no. 6, pp. 645–692, 2008. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10664-008-9076-6>
- [62] L. Yu, S. Ramaswamy, and A. Vaidyanathan, “Understanding the effects of code clones on modularity in software systems,” *Proceedings - Asia-Pacific Software Engineering Conference, APSEC*, vol. 2, pp. 105–111, 2012. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1109/APSEC.2012.49>
- [63] Z. Li, P. Avgeriou, and P. Liang, “A systematic mapping study on technical debt and its management,” *Journal of Systems and Software*, vol. 101, pp. 193–220, 3 2015. [Online]. Available: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jss.2014.12.027https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0164121214002854>
- [64] T. Besker, A. Martini, and J. Bosch, “Managing architectural technical debt: A unified model and systematic literature review,” *Journal of Systems and Software*, vol. 135, pp. 1–16, 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jss.2017.09.025>
- [65] E. Tempero, C. Anslow, J. Dietrich, T. Han, J. Li, M. Lumpe, H. Melton, and J. Noble, “The Qualitas Corpus: a curated collection of Java code for empirical studies,” in *2010 Asia Pacific Software Engineering Conference*. IEEE, 11 2010, pp. 336–345. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1109/APSEC.2010.46>

-
- [66] G. Bavota, A. Qusef, R. Oliveto, A. De Lucia, and D. Binkley, "An empirical analysis of the distribution of unit test smells and their impact on software maintenance," *IEEE International Conference on Software Maintenance, ICSM*, pp. 56–65, 2012. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICSM.2012.6405253>
- [67] C. C. Preston and A. M. Colman, "Optimal number of response categories in rating scales: Reliability, validity, discriminating power, and respondent preferences," *Acta Psychologica*, vol. 104, no. 1, pp. 1–15, 3 2000. [Online]. Available: [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0001-6918\(99\)00050-5](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0001-6918(99)00050-5)
- [68] J. Krosnick and L. Fabrigar, *Designing rating scales for effective measurement in surveys. Survey Measurement and Process Quality*. New York, (NY), USA: John Wiley, 1997.
- [69] G. Moors, N. D. Kieruj, and J. K. Vermunt, "The effect of labeling and numbering of response scales on the likelihood of response bias," *Sociological Methodology*, vol. 44, no. 1, pp. 369–399, 2014. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0081175013516114>
- [70] A. A. Takang, P. A. Grubb, and R. D. Macredie, "The effects of comments and identifier names on program comprehensibility: An experimental investigation," *Journal of Programming Languages*, vol. 4, no. 3, pp. 143–167, 1996. [Online]. Available: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/220398779_The_effects_of_comments_and_identifier_names_on_program_comprehensibility_An_experimental_investigation
- [71] A. Gelman, A. Vehtari, D. Simpson, C. C. Margossian, B. Carpenter, Y. Yao, L. Kennedy, J. Gabry, P. C. Bürkner, and M. Modrák, "Bayesian workflow," *arXiv*, 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2011.01808>
- [72] R. Torkar, C. A. Furia, R. Feldt, F. G. de Oliveira Neto, L. Gren, P. Lenberg, and N. A. Ernst, "A method to assess and argue for practical significance in software engineering," 2020. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1809.09849>
- [73] V. Braun and V. Clarke, "Using thematic analysis in psychology," *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 77–101, 2006. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp063oa>
- [74] B. Amir and P. Ralph, "There is no random sampling in software engineering research," *Proceedings - International Conference on Software Engineering*, no. June, pp. 344–345, 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3183440.3195001>
- [75] C. Wohlin, P. Runeson, M. Höst, M. C. Ohlsson, B. Regnell, and A. Wesslén, *Experimentation in software engineering*. Berlin, Germany: Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2012. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-29044-2>
- [76] D. L. Phillips and K. J. Clancy, "Some effects of "social desirability" in survey studies," *American Journal of Sociology*, vol. 77, no. 5, pp. 921–940, 1972. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1086/225231>

- [77] J. Miller, “Triangulation as a basis for knowledge discovery in software engineering,” *Empirical Software Engineering*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 223–228, 2008. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10664-008-9063-y>
- [78] J. Holvitie, S. A. Licorish, R. O. Spínola, S. Hyrynsalmi, S. G. MacDonell, T. S. Mendes, J. Buchan, and V. Leppänen, “Technical debt and agile software development practices and processes: An industry practitioner survey,” *Information and Software Technology*, vol. 96, no. September 2016, pp. 141–160, 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.infsof.2017.11.015>

A

External Resources

This appendix lists the locations of the artifacts produced and used during the study.

- **RobotResearcher:** The research tool and environment used to conduct the experiment.
 - **Online demo:** <https://bwtse.github.io/RobotResearcher>
 - **Repository (source):** <https://github.com/BWTSE/RobotResearcher/tree/persist1.1>
 - **Snapshot (source):** <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4818494>
- **Scenarios:** The systems tasks and corresponding scenarios that the participants were given.
 - **Repository (source):** <https://github.com/BWTSE/Scenarios/tree/persist1.1>
 - **Snapshot (source):** <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4818493>
- **Data:** The complete set of annotated participant submissions.
 - **Repository (source):** <https://github.com/BWTSE/Data/tree/v1.3>
 - **Snapshot (source):** <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4818445>
- **Replication package:** The replication package for our *Bayesian data analysis*.
 - **Online presentation:** <https://bwtse.github.io/Analysis>
 - **Repository (source):** <https://github.com/BWTSE/Analysis/tree/v1.4>
 - **Snapshot (source):** <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4904595>

B

Task Descriptions

The original task descriptions were written in markdown and rendered to the participants using the **marked** markdown rendering library for **JavaScript** (version 1.2.7). Below you can find a PDF version of the same instructions manually converted with **L^AT_EX**. The original task description can be found in the scenario repository.¹

¹Available at <https://github.com/BWTSE/Scenarios/tree/persist1.1> and <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4818493>.

B.1 The 'Booking' Scenario

Booking task

This system is a simple booking system, where there are currently two types of rooms available: classrooms and group rooms.

Your task is to add a `ComputerClassRoom` class that works like an ordinary classroom, but unlike them, they should also only be available during a specified period of time each day.

The prewritten tests assume the following constructor for the new class: `ComputerClassRoom(String, String, boolean, int, int)` where the arguments represent: the name of the room, a description of the room, whether the room has a projector, the hour of opening, the hour of closing.

Feel free to modify the existing codebase (even the tests) in any way you want as long as you maintain existing functionality.

Task checklist

- Added a `ComputerClassRoom` class that:
 - has all of the same booking limitations that `ClassRoom` has.
 - can only be booked between the opening and closing hours passed to the constructor.
 - can be stored in collections of `Room` and be used as a substitute for `Room`.
- The code compiles and passes all tests in `Main.java`
 - Use the **Run Code** button below to test your solution

Reference for `LocalDateTime` can be found here: [Class LocalDateTime](#)

Tip: the editor supports a [set of shortcuts](#).

B.2 The 'Tickets' Scenario

Tickets Task

This is a system that models a public transport ticket system. It finds the ticket types that are valid for a specific trip and user at a specific time.

Your task is to add a `TicketTypeSeasonalRestricted` class that works like the seasonal ticket type, but unlike them, they should only be valid for users with certain occupations, i.e. students and/or retirees.

The prewritten tests assume the following constructor for the new class: `TicketTypeSeasonalRestricted(String, double, Set<Zone>, Season, Set<User.Occupation>)` where the arguments represent: the ticket name, the ticket price, the zones the ticket is valid for, the season duration which the ticket is valid, and the occupations for which it is valid.

Feel free to modify the existing codebase (even the tests) in any way you want as long as you maintain the existing functionality.

Task checklist

- Added a `TicketTypeSeasonalRestricted` class that:
 - has all of the restraints that `TicketTypeSeasonal` has.
 - only is valid for the set of occupations passed to the constructor.
 - can be stored in collections of `TicketType` and be used as a substitute for `TicketType`.
- The code compiles and passes all tests in `Main.java`
 - Use the **Run Code** button below to test your solution

Tip: the editor supports a [set of shortcuts](#).

C

Survey Questions

This appendix details the answer type and reason for inclusion of each survey question.

C.1 Pre-task Questions

Questions asked before the experiment.

C.1.1 Education Level

Question: What is the highest degree or level of education you have completed?

Answer type: Ordered categorical: 1) None; 2) Some bachelor studies; 3) Bachelor degree; 4) Some master studies; 5) Master degree; 6) Some Ph. D. studies; 7) Ph. D.

Rationale: Considering the vast amounts of time and resources allocated towards educating developers, surely it has some effect on their future professional skills. Perhaps it does not improve their performance in the aspect of software development examined by this study, but if that is the case, then that would be an interesting finding in itself.

C.1.2 Education Field

Question: In what field did you attain that level of education?

Answer type: Text

Rationale: While we have established that the level of education is an interesting factor, in our context, a master's degree in software engineering carries more weight than a Ph.D. in 17th-century Japanese poetry; hence, we should also record the field of that education. Instead of offering a set of categories to choose from (covering all the possibilities would be very difficult), the participant is allowed to enter whatever they like; we group them during data extraction (see Sect. 3.1.10).

C.1.3 Programming Experience

Question: How many years of professional programming experience do you have?

Answer type: Text

Rationale: An experienced developer could have developed a set of good habits that make them more resistant to the allure of quick and dirty solutions. The participants were allowed to describe it in whatever unit of time they saw fit.

C.1.4 Java Experience

Question: How many years of professional experience do you have working with Java?

Answer type: Text.

Rationale: Some development habits may be general, while others are specific to a particular language, in this case: **Java**.

C.1.5 Work Domain

Question: Within what domain did you attain the most work-experience?

Answer type: Text

Rationale: Company culture surrounding code quality and management of technical debt could vary significantly between various companies. E.g., quality control could differ quite a bit between a banking software producer and a game studio.

C.1.6 Workplace Development Practices

Question: My most recent place of employment...

- used peer code reviews
- used pair programming
- tracked technical debt
- had established coding standards

Answer type: Yes/No

Rationale: Some development practices could encourage the formation of good habits. Holvitie et al. found that these four practices, among others, not only were perceived as having a positive impact on the levels of TD but also did, in fact, reduce the amount of TD[78]. While the participants (most likely) would not be implementing these practices while working on the example systems, habits formed by these practices *could* impact their work.

C.2 Post-task Questions

Questions asked after the experiment.

C.2.1 System Quality

Question: The quality (maintainability) of the preexisting code in the [task name] task was:

Answer type: Labeled 7-step Likert scale: Very bad, Somewhat Bad, Bad, Neutral, Good, Somewhat Good, Very Good

Rationale: This question could show whether the participant had consciously noticed the difference in TD level between the two systems they had been extending.

C.2.2 Contribution Quality

Question: The work I did in the [task name] task made the quality (maintainability) of the system:

Answer type: Labeled 7-step Likert scale: Much Worse, Somewhat Worse, Neutral, Somewhat Better, Much Better

Rationale: This question would allow us to examine the correlation between the participants' perception of their work our measures of added TD.

D

Robot Researcher

This appendix discusses the general structure and design of the experiment conduction tool created for the purposes of this study.

D.1 Technical Details

The **RobotResearcher** (RR) tool is built on a client-server architecture. The client, which contains the UI that participants interact with, is a web application built with **JavaScript** and the framework **Vue.js** while the server is built with **golang** using the library. The server and the client communicate through the **HTTP** protocol, and the request flow for a typical participant can be seen in Fig. D.1.

The client makes use of several libraries to provide its functionality. Most notably among those are **Vuetify** which provides most of the UI components, and the **Ace** text editor, which provides the IDE-like text editor, which can be seen in Fig. D.5. As web applications execute within a user's browser, we would not have been able to see execution errors that occurred in a user's browser unless they were somehow reported to us. Therefore we used **sentry**, a third-party service and library, which report any errors that occur in a user's browser along with relevant diagnostics.

The server is quite simple, mainly providing storage, remote code execution for the client, and some basic authorization. The storage features are supported through a connection to a **MongoDB** database. Remote code execution was provided by compiling and executing the user-submitted code on a local **Java Virtual Machine** (JVM).

The compilation and execution of user-submitted code required us to think about security and safety, preferably in multiple layers. The first layer of security is the built-in security manager of the JVM, which allows us to set policies for how the JVM may communicate with the host operating system and external programs. In our case, those policies were configured to deny all interaction with the host except writing to **stderr** and **stdout** (textual output of the program). The second layer of security was achieved by ensuring that the process running the JVM is unprivileged and only has minimal permissions on the file system so that even if a user were able to

Figure D.1: RobotResearcher request flow.

break out of the JVM (which is unlikely but has happened before¹) the impact would be minimal. The last layer of security came from isolating the server application from any other systems. By doing this, the worst damage that a malicious user can do is interfere with the experiment. The client application was hosted from a separate web server to ensure that a potential breach would not result in malicious code being sent to our participants' browsers, guaranteeing their safety.

D.2 Screenshots

Figure D.2: The start page of Robot Researcher. The user is asked for a code and has to accept cookies to get access to the experiment environment

Figure D.3: Welcome screen of Robot Researcher. The screen contains information regarding the experiment and how the participants data will be processed and used.

¹<https://web.archive.org/web/20210424151031/https://www.oracle.com/security-alerts/alert-cve-2013-0422.html>

0 Background info 1 Tickets Task 2 Booking Task 3 Final (4) Questions

What is the highest degree or level of education you have completed? ▾

In what field did you attain that level of education?
e.g. computer science, electrical engineering, software engineering...

How many years of professional programming experience do you have? years
e.g. 1, 2, 3...

How many years of professional experience do you have working with java? years
e.g. 1, 2, 3...

Within what domain did you attain the most work-experience?
e.g. telecom, game development, automotive...

My most recent place of employment...

used peer code reviews. ▾

used pair programming. ▾

tracked technical debt. ▾

had established coding standards. ▾

SUBMIT

Figure D.4: The background survey displayed in Robot Researcher. In addition to the background questions, the image also shows an overview of the experiment at the top of the screen. (the choices are in a drop-down menu indicated by the downward arrow at the right end of the field)

The screenshot displays the 'Tickets Task' interface. On the left, a file selector (7) lists files like Main.java, Season.java, Ticket.java, etc. The central code editor (6) shows Java code for a ticket system. On the right, the task description (1) explains the goal: adding a `TicketTypeSeasonalRestricted` class. Below the description is a task checklist and a 'Run code' button (3). The 'Run output' window (2) shows the result: 'Exit code: null'. A 'Submit' button (4) is at the bottom right. A task view minimization button (5) is located between the code editor and the task description.

Figure D.5: The task view of the RobotResearcher tool. 1: Task description. 2: Execution output. 3: “Run code” button. 4: “Submit” button. 5: Task view minimization button. 6: Code editor. 7: File selector.

The evaluation survey consists of two Likert scales. The first scale is for the 'Tickets' task, with points: Very Bad, Bad, Somewhat Bad, Neutral, Somewhat Good, Good, Very Good. The second scale is for the 'Booking' task, with points: Much Worse, Worse, Somewhat Worse, Neutral, Somewhat Better, Better, Much Better. A 'SUBMIT' button is located at the bottom right of the survey area.

Figure D.6: The task Evaluation survey in Robot Researcher. Task

Thank you for participating!

If you want to receive a copy of the completed thesis or want to participate in a short follow up interview you can use the form below.

Signup for final thesis copy and/or followup interview

Submit this form if you want a copy of the final thesis version or want to participate in a follow up interview

*** Required**

Email address *

Your email _____

I want to receive a copy of the thesis when it is completed

I want to participate in a short (a couple of minutes) followup interview

Data Processing Agreement

Your email is collected to provide you with the completed version of the master thesis and/or to decide a time for a follow up interview depending on the options you selected. William and Hampus are responsible for the collection and processing.

All submitted information will be deleted 1 week after the thesis has been distributed or by the end of 2021, whichever comes first.

If you have any question, want your data corrected, removed, or retrieved you may contact William Levén on email: william@leven.id

I agree to the data processing in accordance to the agreement above.

Submit

Figure D.7: The farewell screen of Robot Researcher. The screen expresses our gratitude towards the participant and offers a digital copy of the final thesis and express interest in participating in a follow-up interview.

E

SonarQube Issues

This appendix lists all SonarQube rules that were triggered while scanning submissions. The following information is listed for each rule.

- The internal SonarQube ID of the rule.
- An example trigger message for the rule.
- If the rule was ignored in the analysis or not.
- If the rule was ignored: a justification to why it was ignored.

E.1 Rules

1. `java:S1220`:
Move this file to a named package.
2. `checkstyle:com.puppycrawl.tools.checkstyle.checks.NoCodeInFileCheck`:
The file does not contain any code.
3. `codehawk:InsufficientModularation`:
This class has InsufficientModularation, there should be over 20 public interfaces, eihther over 30 methods, or has complexity count over 100 times.
Ignored: Is almost impossible to not trigger in a system om this size.
4. `common-java:InsufficientCommentDensity`:
6 more comment lines need to be written to reach the minimum threshold of 25.0% comment density.
Ignored: Documentation was checked manually.
5. `findbugs:BC_EQUALS_METHOD_SHOULD_WORK_FOR_ALL_OBJECTS`:
Equals method for tickets.TicketTypeSeasonalRestricted assumes the argument is of type TicketTypeSeasonalRestricted
6. `findbugs:NP_EQUALS_SHOULD_HANDLE_NULL_ARGUMENT`:
tickets.TicketTypeSeasonalRestricted.equals(Object) does not check for null argument
Ignored: There is another rule that triggers for all unchecked null access.
7. `java:S113`:
Add a new line at the end of this file.

- Ignored:** Formatting that in many cases would have been solved by a proper IDE.
8. `checkstyle:com.puppycrawl.tools.checkstyle.checks.imports.ImportControlCheck:`
Missing an import control file.
Ignored: Base project did not have an import control file and projects of this size does usually not have an import control file.
 9. `checkstyle:com.puppycrawl.tools.checkstyle.checks.modifier.InterfaceMemberImpliedModifierCheck:`
Implied modifier 'abstract' should be explicit.
Ignored: A conflicting rule exists, indicating lack of consensus.
 10. `checkstyle:com.puppycrawl.tools.checkstyle.checks.naming.AbstractClassNameCheck:`
Name 'Filter' must match pattern '^Abstract.+\$'.
 11. `java:S118:`
Rename this abstract class name to match the regular expression “^Abstract[A—Z][a—zA—Z0—9]\$”.*
Ignored: There is another rule addressing abstract class naming.
 12. `java:S1451:`
Add or update the header of this file.
Ignored: Base project did not contain a file header.
 13. `checkstyle:com.puppycrawl.tools.checkstyle.checks.coding.ReturnCountCheck:`
Return count is 3 (max allowed for non-void methods/lambda is 2).
 14. `java:S1106:`
Move this left curly brace to the beginning of next line of code.
Ignored: Cosmetic formatting rule.
 15. `checkstyle:com.puppycrawl.tools.checkstyle.checks.javadoc.JavadocPackageCheck:`
Missing package-info.java file.
Ignored: Base project did not have a package-info.java file and projects of this size does usually not have a package-info.java file.
 16. `checkstyle:com.puppycrawl.tools.checkstyle.checks.javadoc.WriteTagCheck:`
Type Javadoc comment is missing null tag.
Ignored: Rule is about javadoc.
 17. `findbugs:EQ_DOESNT_OVERRIDE_EQUALS:`
booking.ComputerClassRoom doesn't override ClassRoom.equals(Object)
Ignored: Existence of equals method is checked manually.
 18. `java:S1228:`
Add a 'package-info.java' file to document the '.submission/tickets' package
Ignored: Base project did not have a package-info.java file and projects of this size does usually not have a package-info.java file.
 19. `java:S2039:`

- Explicitly declare the visibility for "start".*
20. `checkstyle:com.puppycrawl.tools.checkstyle.checks.coding.DeclarationOrderCheck:`
Variable access definition in wrong order.
 21. `common-java:InsufficientLineCoverage:`
2 more lines of code need to be covered by tests to reach the minimum threshold of 65.0% lines coverage.
Ignored: Test coverage was not measured.
 22. `fb-contrib:FCCD_FIND_CLASS_CIRCULAR_DEPENDENCY:`
Class booking.ComputerClassRoom has a circular dependency with other classes
 23. `checkstyle:com.puppycrawl.tools.checkstyle.checks.imports.UnusedImportsCheck:`
Unused import - java.time.temporal.ChronoField.
Ignored: The IDE usually assist the developer with removing unused imports.
 24. `checkstyle:com.puppycrawl.tools.checkstyle.checks.whitespace.SingleSpaceSeparatorCheck:`
Use a single space to separate non-whitespace characters.
Ignored: Cosmetic formatting rule.
 25. `checkstyle:com.puppycrawl.tools.checkstyle.checks.design.VisibilityModifierCheck:`
Variable 'room' must be private and have accessor methods.
 26. `checkstyle:com.puppycrawl.tools.checkstyle.checks.modifier.ClassMemberImpliedModifierCheck:`
Implied modifier 'static' should be explicit.
Ignored: A conflicting rule exists, indicating lack of consensus.
 27. `checkstyle:com.puppycrawl.tools.checkstyle.checks.sizes.LineLengthCheck:`
Line is longer than 100 characters (found 111).
Ignored: Using rule with 120 character limit instead.
 28. `java:S125:`
This block of commented-out lines of code should be removed.
 29. `java:S2259:`
A "NullPointerException" could be thrown; "o" is nullable here.
 30. `checkstyle:com.puppycrawl.tools.checkstyle.checks.coding.UnnecessaryParenthesesCheck:`
Unnecessary parentheses around expression.
 31. `java:S1068:`
Remove this unused "hO" private field.
 32. `java:S1120:`
Make this line start after 8 spaces to indent the code consistently.
Ignored: The IDE usually assists the user with indentation.
 33. `java:S4274:`
Replace this assert with a proper check.

34. `findbugs:URF_UNREAD_FIELD:`
Unread field: booking.ComputerClassRoom.closes
35. `java:S1105:`
Move this left curly brace to the end of previous line of code.
Ignored: Cosmetic formatting rule.
36. `java:S1172:`
Remove this unused method parameter "user".
37. `checkstyle:com.puppycrawl.tools.checkstyle.checks.`
`NewlineAtEndOfFileCheck:`
File does not end with a newline.
Ignored: Formatting that in many cases would have been solved by a proper IDE.
38. `checkstyle:com.puppycrawl.tools.checkstyle.checks.design.`
`DesignForExtensionCheck:`
Class 'Ticket' looks like designed for extension (can be subclassed), but the method 'getTicketType' does not have javadoc that explains how to do that safely. If class is not designed for extension consider making the class 'Ticket' final or making the method 'getTicketType' static/final/abstract/empty, or adding allowed annotation for the method.
Ignored: Rule is about javadoc.
39. `checkstyle:com.puppycrawl.tools.checkstyle.checks.indentation.`
`CommentsIndentationCheck:`
Block comment has incorrect indentation level 4, expected is 1, indentation should be the same level as line 76.
Ignored: The IDE usually assists the user with indentation.
40. `checkstyle:com.puppycrawl.tools.checkstyle.checks.indentation.`
`IndentationCheck:`
'if' child has incorrect indentation level 12, expected level should be 16.
Ignored: The IDE usually assists the user with indentation.
41. `codehawk:AvoidUnutilizedAbstraction:`
It is Unutilized Abstraction
Ignored: Rule seems broken and triggers even when the specified conditions are satisfied.
42. `fb-contrib:WOC_WRITE_ONLY_COLLECTION_FIELD:`
Class booking.ComputerClassRoom creates and initializes a collection but never reads or gains information from it
43. `java:S1108:`
Move this "else" keyword to a new dedicated line.
Ignored: Cosmetic formatting rule.
44. `fb-contrib:SEO_SUBOPTIMAL_EXPRESSION_ORDER:`
Method tickets.
TicketTypeSeasonalRestricted.equals(Object) orders expressions in a conditional in a sub optimal way
45. `java:S103:`

- Split this 144 characters long line (which is greater than 120 authorized).*
46. java:S1128:
Remove this unused import 'java.util.EnumSet'.
Ignored: The IDE usually assist the developer with removing unused imports.
 47. java:S2309:
This file has 0 lines of code.
Ignored: Another rule exists that checks for empty files.
 48. common-java:DuplicatedBlocks:
1 duplicated blocks of code must be removed.
Ignored: Duplication was checked manually.
 49. java:S105:
Replace all tab characters in this file by sequences of white-spaces.
Ignored: Cosmetic formatting rule.
 50. java:S1067:
Reduce the number of conditional operators (4) used in the expression (maximum allowed 3).
 51. java:S1659:
Declare "closesAt" on a separate line.
Ignored: There is another rule checking that variables are declared at separate lines.
 52. java:S864:
Add parentheses to make the operator precedence explicit.
 53. checkstyle:com.puppycrawl.tools.checkstyle.checks.imports.ImportOrderCheck:
Wrong order for 'java.time.LocalDate' import.
Ignored: Order of imports are often handled by the IDE
 54. fb-contrib:NSE_NON_SYMMETRIC_EQUALS:
Equals method tickets.TicketTypeSeasonalRestricted.equals(Object) compares this object against other types in a non symmetric way
 55. fb-contrib:OCP_OVERLY_CONCRETE_PARAMETER:
booking.Interval.isDuring(LocalDateTime): 1st parameter " could be declared as java.time.chrono.ChronoLocalDateTime instead Rule is generally good even if it's wrong for the chronofield.
 56. findbugs:EQ_CHECK_FOR_OPERAND_NOT_COMPATIBLE_WITH_THIS:
tickets.TicketTypeSeasonalRestricted.equals(Object) checks for operand being a TicketTypeSeasonal
 57. java:S1698:
Use the "equals" method if value comparison was intended.
 58. java:S2097:
Add a type test to this method.
 59. checkstyle:com.puppycrawl.tools.checkstyle.checks.annotation.AnnotationOnSameLineCheck:

Annotation 'Override' should be on the same line with its target.

Ignored: Cosmetic formatting rule.

60. `checkstyle:com.puppycrawl.tools.checkstyle.checks.coding.`

`MultipleVariableDeclarationsCheck:`

Each variable declaration must be in its own statement.

61. `checkstyle:com.puppycrawl.tools.checkstyle.checks.whitespace.`

`FileTabCharacterCheck:`

File contains tab characters (this is the first instance).

Ignored: Cosmetic formatting rule.

62. `java:S1126:`

Replace this if-then-else statement by a single return statement.

63. `java:S2159:`

Remove this call to "equals"; comparisons between unrelated types always return false.

Ignored: Rule is broken and reports false positives.